

Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication Plan at EU & National Levels

M6/March 2023

Author(s):
Dajana Vujaklija, Milica Lukić, Milica Trajković
(BIOS)

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101060212.

Project Full Title	A EUROPEAN-WIDE NETWORK OF PILOT FARMERS IMPLEMENTING AND DEMONSTRATING CLIMATE SMART SOLUTIONS FOR A CARBON NEUTRAL EUROPE
GA number	101060212
Type of Action	Coordination and Support Action (CSA)
Project Duration	84 months
Project Start Date	01.10.2022.
Project Website	climatefarmdemo.eu
Deliverable Title	Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication Plan at EU & National Levels
Deliverable Submission Date	31.03.2023
Status	Final
Dissemination Level	PU – Public
Deliverable Lead	BIOS
Authors	Dajana Vujaklija, Milica Lukić, Milica Trajković (BIOS)
Contact	dajana.vujaklija@biosense.rs; milica.lukic@biosense.rs; trajkovic@biosense.rs
Work Package	WP8
Keywords	Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication, Outreach, Media, Targets

Disclaimer

The content of this deliverable represents the views of the author(s) only and does not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. The European Union institutions and bodies or any person acting on their behalf are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

List of Abbreviations

CFD	Climate Farm Demo
CS	Climate Smart
CSF	Climate Smart Farming
CFA	Climate Farm Advisor
NC	National Coordinator
PDF	Pilot Farm Demo
WP	Work Package
AKIS	Agriculture Knowledge and Innovation Systems
CS-AKIS	Climate Smart AKIS
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
KE	Knowledge Exchange
AMM	Adaptation and Mitigation Measures
LL	Living Lab
MRV	Monitoring Reporting and Verification

Table of Contents

Abstract.....	9
1. Introduction	10
2. Objectives & Target Groups.....	12
2.1 Project Objectives	13
2.2 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Objectives	13
2.3 Target Groups Description.....	14
2.3.1 Identified Target Groups	14
2.3.2 Key Messages to Target Groups	15
2.3.3 Expected Impact & Outputs for Target Groups.....	16
3. Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Tools	18
3.1 Visual Identity.....	19
3.1.1 CFD Logo	19
3.1.2 Corporate Colours	19
3.1.3 Document Templates	20
3.2 FarmDemo Logo Redesign.....	21
3.3 Practice Abstracts	23
3.4 Newsletters	23
3.4.1 Content.....	24
3.4.2 General information.....	24
3.5 Press Releases.....	25
3.6 Editorial materials	26
3.7 Multimedia Materials	27
3.8 Infographics	27
4. Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Channels	30
4.1 Climate Farm Demo Website & Online Content Repository.....	31
4.2 CFD Network Events	31
4.3 Social Media	31

5. Social Media Strategy	45
5.1 Objectives	46
5.2 Social Media Platforms	46
5.2.1 Survey Among NCs.....	46
5.2.2 Twitter.....	48
5.2.3 LinkedIn.....	48
5.2.4 Facebook.....	49
5.2.5 YouTube.....	50
5.3 Target Audiences on Social Media & Key Messages.....	52
5.4 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	53
5.5 Content Strategy	53
5.5.1 Defining Content.....	53
5.5.2 Growth Hacking Strategy	53
5.5.3 Content Calendar & Translations	54
5.5.4 Practical Tips & Suggested Hashtag List	54
5.6 Monitoring & Evaluation.....	55
6. Dissemination and Exploitation of Project Results	56
7. DEC Plans on National Level.....	58
8. Monitoring & Evaluation	61
8.1 Management of DEC activities	62
8.2 DEC Monitoring System	67
8.2.1 List of WP8 Deliverables and Milestones.....	67
8.2.2 Monitoring system	68
8.2.3. Result Indicators.....	68
9. Conclusions.....	70
10. Annexes	72
Annex 1: CFD Corporate Identity Manual.....	73
Annex 2: Document Templates	81
1. Deliverable template.....	81

2. Working document template	85
3. Meeting agenda template.....	86
4. Meeting minutes template	87
5. Milestone template	88
6. PPT presentation template.....	89
Annex 3: NC Social Media Survey.....	90
Annex 4: DEC Plans on National Level	94
Annex 5: Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Activities Tracker.....	98

List of Tables and Figures

Table 1. CFD objectives.....	13
Table 2. Target groups overview	15
Table 3. Target groups & key messages/benefit	16
Table 4. Target groups, impact and outputs	16
Table 5. Newsletter overview	24
Table 6. CFD partners' social media.....	32
Table 7. Target audiences and key messages	52
Table 8. Social media KPIs	53
Table 9. Key Exploitable Results (KER)	57
Table 10. Partner organisations' communication officers	64
Table 11. WP8 deliverables	67
Table 12. WP8 Milestones	67
Table 13. CFD result indicators	69
Figure 1. CFD DEC objectives	14
Figure 2. CFD logo.....	19
Figure 3. CFD corporate colours.....	20
Figure 4. CFD template examples	21
Figure 5. New FarmDemo logo variations on white and black backgrounds.....	22
Figure 6. Example of the application of the new FarmDemo logo on documents	23
Figure 7. New and old logotypes	23
Figure 8. Flyers for farmers.....	26
Figure 9. CFD infographics	29
Figure 10. Social media usage reported by NCs	47
Figure 11. Estimated social media usage among farmers.....	47
Figure 12. CFD Twitter account	48

Figure 13. CFD LinkedIn account	49
Figure 14. CFD Facebook page.....	50
Figure 15. FarmDemo YouTube Channel.....	51
Figure 16. Segment from the Annual DEC plan on national level template	59
Figure 17. Segment from Annual DEC plan on national level template: how national coordinators will use the annual plans for i) planning of DEC activities and ii) requesting material and inputs from other partners	60
Figure 18. Relation between planning, executing and reporting on DEC activities	68

Abstract

Deliverable D8.1 presents the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan, the purpose of which is to identify and elaborate on strategies for communication and wide distribution of project results on both European and national levels to accelerate the uptake of climate change adaptation and mitigation measures among practitioners. This is the first version of plan, submitted in M6 of the project. The primary aim is to successfully promote project activities, disseminate results and outputs, exploit knowledge, approaches and solutions developed within the project and raise awareness of Climate Smart Farming and Climate Mitigation measures among relevant target audiences.

This document describes various communication tools and channels designed to support the DEC objectives (project website, social media channels, external and internal newsletters, visual identity and more). It is a living document, scheduled for two revisions: one in M26 (D8.6) and another in M50 (D8.8), allowing for re-evaluations and improvements.

As the leader of WP8 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication, the BioSense Institute (BIOS) will lead the implementation of the DEC strategy with support from all project partners. A plan for monitoring & evaluation will be used to follow the progress and quality of DEC activities, which are designed to allow CFD partners to disseminate their results and engage with stakeholders.

Chapter 1

1. Introduction

This chapter provides a short summary of the CFD project, a general overview of the DEC plan and the deliverable structure. It will allow the reader to understand what they can expect from the document and where specific pieces of information can be found within it.

Climate Farm Demo is a unique pan-European network of Pilot Demo Farmers (PDFs) covering 27 countries and all pedo-climatic areas. Its overall aim is to accelerate the adoption of Climate Smart Farming (CSF) practices and solutions by farmers and all actors of the Climate Smart Agriculture Knowledge & Innovation Systems (AKIS), with a view of adapting agricultural production systems to climate change and of achieving a carbon neutral agricultural sector by 2050, thereby meeting the targets of the EU Climate strategy. To reach this objective, the project adopts a Multi-Actor approach by connecting 1,500 Pilot Demo Farmers and their Climate Farm Advisors (CFAs) at European and national levels to increase knowledge exchange & cross-fertilisation in their respective AKIS. Technical and social innovations covering a broad range of thematic areas will be demonstrated to the wider farming community across six annual demo campaigns (4,500 demo-events) supporting interactive and peer-to-peer learning.

The present deliverable thoroughly describes strategies (EU and national level) and tools and channels selected as most suitable for this project and its approach regarding dissemination, communication and exploitation. It will be fine-tuned with time, with two revisions scheduled later in the project (M26 and M50). The document also offers guidelines for adhering to the project's visual identity and utilising social media to engage with different target groups (farmers, advisory services, economic actors of the supply chains, research & education, EIP-AGRI Service Pint & CAP Networks, policy makers, and consumers & citizens).

Divided into chapters, the deliverable is organised to cover all the matters in a way that is easy to follow.

- Chapter 1 – Introduction provides a brief overview of the project, the deliverable and the document structure.
- Chapter 2 – Objectives & Target Groups describes the overall project objectives, target groups, key messages and expected outputs to help visualise the potential of CFD.
- Chapter 3 – Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication Tools focuses on tools created to ensure effective D&C on national and EU levels and ways of supporting all WPs on their path towards achieving the envisaged results.
- Chapter 4 – Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Channels explains how selected channels will be managed to reach as many audiences as possible and encourage them to engage.
- Chapter 5 – Social Media Strategy shows the strategy created to boost the project visibility among the target audiences and beyond and raise as much awareness as possible about the ways in which CSF practices can reduce adverse environmental impact.
- Chapter 6 – Dissemination and Exploitation of Project Results describes how all the knowledge and results accumulated throughout the project will be gathered, disseminated and exploited.
- Chapter 7 – DEC Plans on National Level offers information on the importance of national C&D, its main aspects and activities and the purpose and structure of DEC plans on national level.
- Chapter 8 – Monitoring & Evaluation is dedicated to the management of DEC activities, looking at the tasks of WP8 and Communication Officers appointed by each partner. This chapter also lists all the deliverables and milestones pertaining to WP8, the monitoring system and result indicators.
- Chapter 9 – Conclusions summarises the main takeaways after gathering and analysing everything necessary for an effective DEC plan.
- Chapter 10 – Annexes contains extra documentation that was previously described in the deliverable.

Chapter 2

2. Objectives & Target Groups

This section explores the overall project objectives, target groups, key messages and expected outputs to help visualise the potential of CFD.

2.1 Project Objectives

Climate Farm Demo overall aims to (1) network Pilot-Demo-Farmers (PDFs) to boost CSF knowledge exchange and cross-fertilisation among agricultural sectors and EU and national Agriculture Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS), (2) support and advise PDFs in implementing and demonstrating CSF practices to increase innovation uptake and finally, (3) to incentivise the adoption of CSF practices across Europe thanks to standardised methodologies and relevant rewarding mechanisms that will support farmers in their systemic transition.

Climate Farm Demo project has specific objectives, shown in the following table.

Table 1. CFD objectives

No	Climate Farm Demo objectives
Objective 1	To build and manage a well-connected network of 1,500 Pilot Demo Farmers (PDFs) and Climate Farm Advisors (CFAs) covering 24 EU Member States, 1 associated country (Republic of Serbia), Switzerland and UK, and structured across pedo-climatic areas, agricultural sectors and Adaptation & Mitigation thematic areas, accelerating the knowledge exchanges (KE) and capacity building within and between Climate Smart AKIS (CS-AKIS).
Objective 2	To support 1,500 Pilot Demo Farmers, through tailored, regular and long-term advise , in planning, implementing and monitoring their farm Adaptation and Mitigation Measures (AMM) by using a standardised and adapted methodology, towards the achievement of 35% GHG emission reduction
Objective 3	To support the delivery of 4,500 high-quality demonstration events in a multi-actor setting in the 1,500 PDFs during 6 annual demonstration campaigns in 27 EU countries , thereby resulting in substantially increased uptake and application of CSF approaches and practices by other Pilot Demo Farmers and average farmers
Objective 4	To co-create a set of new and innovative CSF solutions in 10 multi-actor Living Labs (LL) covering all adaptation and mitigation measures and located in all European pedo-climatic areas ; explore lessons learned on implementation of LL approach embedded in national or regional CS-AKIS for scaling and future multi-actor partnerships engaged in innovation and adoption of CSF.
Objective 5	To build a common framework on adaptation & mitigation by collecting and comparing climate and carbon tools across Europe to elaborate (i) a harmonised carbon assessment method & environmental adaptation indicators , to define (ii) a common MRV methodology and (iii) guidelines for climate adaptation and mitigation.
Objective 6	To analyse rewarding mechanisms that support (i) the adaptation and risk reduction of farming practices to climate change, (ii) the mitigation of all GHG emissions including the carbon sequestration in soils and agricultural landscapes in order to build capacity of PDFs and CFAs and to support a wide use and adoption of rewarding mechanisms as a lever for transformation based on systemic analysis of farmers' needs
Objective 7	To build a network of (i) related EU projects , (ii) Flagship EU initiatives and (iii) Policy makers (at EU and national levels) to give visibility to the project , create cooperation , integrate research and knowledge from other projects, produce common policy and operational recommendations and prepare a sustainability strategy for the whole Climate Farm Demo network.
Objective 8	To develop Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) plans and an integrated knowledge reservoir (KR) & associated tools that accelerate the scaling and uptake of climate change adaptation & mitigation measures among practitioners and their understanding by the society in the 27 European CS-AKIS and at EU level

2.2 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Objectives

The overall project objective is to widely communicate, disseminate and exploit innovative solutions for reducing farming activities' impact on climate change. Thus, all actions will result in the delivery of practical and implementable solutions and materials for the relevant actors and stakeholders.

The main objective of the CFD project's Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication is to accelerate the scaling up and uptake of climate change adaptation and mitigation measures (AMMs) among practitioners and understanding of AMMs (among the general public) in the 27 EU Climate Smart AKIS and at the EU level through i) planning; ii) implementation; and iii) capacity building to spread the project outputs among partners and at the national and EU level. Project results, tools and materials – guidelines, EIP-AGRI practice abstracts, testimonials and trainings – will be stored in an online knowledge reservoir. Coupled with innovative streaming, visualisation and interactive engagement, it forms a starting line for uptake and further exploitation of results. More specifically, the project's DEC objectives are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. CFD DEC objectives

2.3 Target Groups Description

A good definition and elaboration of the target audience helps us better understand who we are trying to reach and allows the communication to be tailored specifically to the people it is intended to engage. Effective communication is about more than just delivering a message; it is about delivering the right message to the right audience. If the audience is not properly defined, or the messages are not properly crafted, the project may not resonate with the intended recipients. By understanding the target groups, DEC activities can be customised to better cater to the needs and interests of the audience, resulting in higher rates of engagement and making the overall communication strategy more effective and efficient.

2.3.1 Identified Target Groups

The project has identified seven main target groups that will benefit from the results generated by the project. Firstly, project aiming at engaging **farmers** across the Europe. It will activate at least 1,500 PDFs that will be registered on the Portal and that will be hosting a total of 4,500 farm demonstrations. Besides farmers running the PDFs, engaged in trainings and knowledge transfer activities, the project will engage far more farmers who will be reached through demonstration events, or benefit from tailored CS advice delivered by CS Advisors. Secondly, Climate Farm **Advisors** of the 27 countries will be networked and annually trained along the project lifetime to gain new knowledge and skills to properly support and facilitate farm transformation towards adoption of climate smart farming practices. The project will also address **policy makers** on local, national and EU level, enabling the improvement of the design and implementation of rewarding mechanisms to provide better answers to stakeholders needs and transition requirements for GHG emission reduction. It will create policy recommendations and deliver policy briefs translated in all national languages and adapted to local contexts. Moreover, the **economic actors of the supply chains** will benefit from participation in farmers networks which will enable them to better understanding farmers needs and challenges and improve their services. By involving **academia and research institutions**, the project increases the multi-actor approach that accelerate the genesis of relevant CSF practices and raises awareness of students on the capacity of the farming sector to sustainably manage lands. And finally, **society at large** will directly benefit from climate-friendly, resilient farming practices adopted in the EU and associated countries, and the project is hoping that 50% of the European population will be aware of the key societal role and outstanding potential of agriculture to reduce the impact of human activities on climate change by 2040.

Table 2. Target groups overview

Target group	Description
Farmers	The project will mobilise European farmers through 4500 on-farm and virtual demonstrations organised in 27 countries across Europe that will enable knowledge sharing and peer learning to accelerate adoption of CSF practices. A total of 1500 Pilot Demo Farms will be directly involved in project activities, delivering demonstrations and participating in capacity building activities.
Advisory services	The project will gather together 1000 advisors from 27 countries who will use the training modules, methods and tools developed under the project to support farmers both in the implementation of adaptation and mitigation measures and s in the organisation and facilitation of on-farm demonstration events to increase their relevance and impact.
Economic actors of the supply chains	Commercial actors of the supply chains will be able to accelerate the potential of the carbon market but also to connect to a wide range of actors in the national AKIS.
EIP-AGRI Service Point & CAP Networks	The project will partner with 24 National CAP Networks to increase communication in the national AKIS and to promote demo-events that will take place along the project.
Policy makers	The project will establish a dialogue with policy makers at national level (ministries) EU (EC) levels and local authorities.
Research & education	Consortium involves applied research organisations (10) and research institutes and universities (16) who will work in multi-actor partnerships on knowledge generation. Project will have an impact on a wider research community across Europe by increasing the capacity of researchers to perform farm assessment and to work on carbon and MRV methodologies.
Consumers & citizens	Through the use of national and European media channels, project will raise awareness among consumers and general audience about the role of farmers in climate change mitigation and adaptation.

2.3.2 Key Messages to Target Groups

Key messages for each target group are the most relevant aspects of the project that resonate with a targeted audience. Key messages reflect specific needs, preferences, and values of each target group and tailor the communication according to what the project can offer them. When messages are crafted in a way that resonates with the audience, they are more likely to take action than if we were just repeating overall project objectives and ambition. However, the messages presented in Table 3, reflect the overall project ambition and how the specific target group could benefit from the project in general and should be further narrowed for attracting the audience to specific project activity.

Table 3. Target groups & key messages/benefit

Target group	Key message / benefit
Farmers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> By implementing cost-effective adaptation & mitigation measures reducing GHG emissions and enhancing carbon sequestration in ecosystems, your farm can become more sustainable. Get involved in national and EU networks of PDFs to exchange innovative knowledge. Benefit from tailored advice and innovative tools to reduce your climate impact. Be rewarded for your climate smart practices and ensure economically viable business.
Advisory services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide better support and advice to farmers by benefiting of innovative tools, methods and trainings related to climate smart farming Participate in national and EU multi-actor networks that stimulate knowledge exchange and genesis of new solutions.
Economic actors of the supply chains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participate in farmers networks and connect to a wide range of actors & stakeholders in the national AKIS Reward farmers for their capacity to reduce GHG emissions and to increase carbon storage.
Research & education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Co-create new solutions with a wide range of stakeholders engaged in sustainable transitions. Teach new generations about the role of sustainable farming practices to reduce the climate impact.
EIP-AGRI Service Point & CAP Networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accelerate knowledge exchange among the project other AKIS actors and disseminate practical-oriented solutions, tools and methods. Stimulate innovation partnerships in the European and national AKIS
Policy makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Get evidence of the effectiveness of climate smart practices for mitigation of GHG emission and adaptation to climate change. Benefit from a wide range of recommendations on networking, demos and rewarding mechanisms.
Consumers & citizens	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased awareness about the potential of the farming sector to mitigate GHG emissions and increase carbon sequestration. Support sustainable agricultural production.

2.3.3 Expected Impact & Outputs for Target Groups

Table 4. Target groups, impact and outputs

Target groups	Impact for target group	Outputs for target group
Farmers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Farmers & all relevant AKIS actors will be better connected, and cross-fertilisation of CSF practices will be increased. Increased awareness and engagement by farmers in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Web-based platform aggregating relevant knowledge on climate mitigation measures and sustainable farming A guidebook for rewarding mechanisms

	<p>sustainable transition towards CSF practices.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Accelerated adoption of CSF practices through peer-to-peer learning and rewarding mechanisms. ▪ Co-creation of new and innovative solutions in multi-actor and multi-stakeholders LL environments. ▪ Network multiplier effects achieved through leveraging of existing dissemination channels 	<p>Climate Farm Demo training toolbox</p> <p>EIP-AGRI Practice Abstracts</p> <p>High quality videos on the FarmDemo YouTube channel</p> <p>Network of 1,500 PDFs enabling knowledge exchange and peer learning</p>
Advisory services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Increased advisors' capacity to support farmers and improve business models for climate smart farming ▪ Strengthen the key role of advisors in national and regional CS-AKIS and comply with the CAP objectives ▪ Network multiplier effects achieved through leveraging of existing dissemination channels 	<p>Innovative training modules, methods and tools to support farmers to adopt climate smart farming practices</p>
Economic actors of the supply chains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Improved understanding of farmers needs and challenges and improvement of their services. ▪ Accelerate the potential of the carbon market ▪ Network multiplier effects achieved through leveraging of existing dissemination channels 	<p>Knowledge reservoir of contextualised CSF practices, solutions, business models, methods and tools easily accessible the value chain actors, along with other target groups</p>
Research & education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Increase multi-actor partnerships on the long-term that accelerate the genesis of relevant CSF practices ▪ Raise students 'awareness on the capacity of the farming sector to sustainably manage lands 	<p>EIP-AGRI Practice Abstracts</p> <p>Climate Farm Demo training toolbox</p>
EIP-AGRI Service Point & CAP Networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Reach a critical mass and engage a wide network of relevant stakeholder groups in the cross-fertilisation ▪ Use their dissemination channels to achieve network multiplier effects for large-scale sustainable transition at European level 	<p>EIP-AGRI Practice Abstracts</p> <p>Climate Farm Demo training toolbox</p>
Policy makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Design and promote new policy incentives that accelerate farmers engagement in climate smart farming and sustainable transition ▪ Fund further innovative climate smart farming projects to reach the objectives of the EU Climate Strategy 	<p>Policy recommendations at all levels (EU, MS, Regions)</p>
Consumers & citizens	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Well-informed citizen towards a behavioural and mindset shift towards sustainable transition ▪ Diminish agri-bashing thanks to well informed citizen and consumers connected in National AKIS 	<p>Increased awareness of farmer challenges & actions among the civil society</p>

Chapter 3

3. Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Tools

The DEC strategy aims to reach a critical mass of actors and stakeholders across the EU territories and beyond, therefore all DEC material will be designed to have a broad impact in the 27 countries. This chapter focuses on tools created to ensure effective D&C on national and EU levels and ways to support all WPs in achieving the envisaged results.

3.1 Visual Identity

3.1.1 CFD Logo

Climate Farm Demo aims to strengthen European farmers' capacities to implement, demonstrate and uptake Climate Smart Farming practice across the EU. That involves a notable network of PDFs and Climate Farm Advisors from different agricultural sectors and Adaptation Mitigation, the logo was designed to symbolise the connectedness of agriculture, climate action, technology and learning with the circular shape and the closeness of the multi coloured lines.

Figure 2. CFD logo

All dissemination materials will feature the logo, along with the EU emblem and a statement that the project has received funding from the Horizon Europe program.

More information about the correct usage of the logo and typography is available in the Corporate Identity Manual (Annex 1).

3.1.2 Corporate Colours

The Climate Farm Demo colour palette includes different shades of green and yellow/orange as colours very much present in nature and often associated with it. Any graphic element that is built around the brand (graphics, icons, etc should preferably use this colour combination).

The exact colours and their colour system codes are presented in the figure below.

Figure 3. CFD corporate colours

3.1.3 Document Templates

Several document templates containing the necessary visual elements are available in the project's designated workspace (MS Teams). That includes:

- Deliverable template
- Working document template
- Meeting agenda template
- Meeting minutes template
- Milestone template
- PPT presentation template

Title of the document in two or more lines
 Subtitle in one line – optional – 2nd level

14 January 2021

Author(s):
 Name Surname, ORGANISATION ACRONYM

Funded by the European Union

This project has received funding from the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101060212.

Meeting Name

Date:	Time:
Place:	
Organiser:	
Meeting with:	

Agenda

[time] [subject]
 [time] [subject]
 [time] [subject]
 [time] [subject]
 [time] [subject]
 [time] [subject]
 [time] [subject]

This project has received funding from the European Union under Grant Agreement No 101060212.

Click to add title

Click to add subtitle

Author

Figure 4. CFD template examples

To access the full version of all the templates, see Annex 2 of this deliverable.

3.2 FarmDemo Logo Redesign

FarmDemo was established by three related projects: NEFERTITI, PLAID and AgriDemoF2F. In 2021, IPM WORKS project joined the FarmDemo family, which continues to grow Climate Farm Demo. As

new projects come and previous projects end, the focus and rationale behind the farm demo also changes, resulting in the need to refresh the visual identity of the FarmDemo to better reflect new and upcoming projects. The new FarmDemo logo has a modernised appearance achieved through i) the new typeface – the light version of the font reflects a contemporary yet resilient approach of sharing knowledge through demonstrations; ii) more open and stylised sign – enabling, metaphorically speaking, a knowledge flow from FarmDemo to other projects and from projects outside FarmDemo to projects that are a part of the FarmDemo family.

Figure 5. New FarmDemo logo variations on white and black backgrounds

Figure 6. Example of the application of the new FarmDemo logo on documents

Figure 7. New and old logotypes

3.3 Practice Abstracts

The resulting innovative knowledge from this project will feed into the EIP-AGRI (The agricultural European Innovation Partnership) website for broad dissemination to practitioners. End-user material will be produced in the form of a number of summaries for practitioners in the EIP common format ("practice abstracts"). The project details will also be submitted to the platform with the first deliverable submission. The National Coordinators will produce at least 10 practice abstract each, following the guidance and templates for practice abstracts available on the EIP-AGRI website: <http://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/content/eip-agri-common-format>. Practice abstracts will be reported in three batches, each presenting 100 pieces: D8.5 EIP practice abstracts – batch 1, delivered in M12; D8.7 EIP practice abstracts – batch 2, submitted in M48; and D8.9 EIP practice abstracts – batch 3, submitted in M72.

3.4 Newsletters

Climate Farm Demo WP8 will create and disseminate newsletters to provide the latest updates on the progress, activities and available project results towards project stakeholders and broader audiences within the field of climate mitigation and agriculture across EU – farming community, research and academia, advisors, agro-businesses, policymakers. Two types of project newsletter will be developed – internal, focusing on Consortium members, and external, focusing on target audience outside the project.

The main purpose of the external CFD newsletter is to:

- Build relationships with relevant stakeholders.
- Keep the audience informed about project progress, project activities including upcoming events and capacity building and knowledge exchange opportunities,
- Disseminate project results,
- Boost social media following,
- Increase website traffic.

The main purpose of the internal CFD newsletter is to:

- Provide project partners with concise information about the overall progress of project implementation,
- Disseminate the newest project results towards all consortium members,
- Provide project partners with a summarised list of upcoming activities,
- Provide project partners with the updates on new tools and materials developed under the project,
- Encourage further dissemination of project results and promotion of project activities by all partners.

3.4.1 Content

The external newsletters communicate information on all project activities relevant for project stakeholders and wider audience, project results, training materials, announcements of farm demonstration events, online and on-spot training, workshops and webinars, upcoming conferences and other relevant information. Each issue of the newsletter will reflect the overall project progress and all ExCom members will be invited to contribute with relevant information and results achieved. Relevant information on all 12 adaptation and mitigation thematic areas will be included in creation of newsletter content. The internal newsletter will be focused on presenting an overview of the achieved results and reminding the partners about upcoming activities. Moreover, it will summarise and link in one place all tools and materials developed that can help all the partners in their day-to-day activities. All WP leaders will be invited to contribute to the content creation and use the opportunity of issuing the internal newsletter to inform the consortium about the progress made under all WPs.

3.4.2 General information

- Newsletters are managed by the BioSense Institute via the Mailchimp service, with contributions by ExCom members and other project partners when relevant.
- The language of the newsletter is English. Each National Coordinator can then decide to translate the content in the local language and disseminate it further on their channels (i.e., organisational website or mailing list).
- There is an embedded subscription form on the project website to enable the audience to sign up for the newsletter.
- The total number of newsletters is 56, while the dynamic of publishing is designed in a way to reflect the content-first approach which allows WP8 members to adapt the frequency of publishing based on project progress and planned project activities.

Table 5. Newsletter overview

YEAR 1	YEAR 2	YEAR 3	YEAR 4	YEAR 5	YEAR 6	YEAR 7
--------	--------	--------	--------	--------	--------	--------

External newsletter no.	3-4	4-5	4-6	4-6	4-6	4-6	5-6
External newsletter focus areas	Project ambition; Practice abstracts	Demonstration events Report on the first Climate Farm Demo campaign; Training modules; Digital repository for carbon & environmental models, methods & tools	Synergies with other projects Demonstration events; Report on the second Climate Farm Demo campaign; Manual for application of AMPs on farm; Farms GHG accounting methodology and guidelines	Demonstration events; Report on the third Climate Farm Demo campaign; Synergies with other projects	Practice abstracts; Demonstration events; Report on the fourth Climate Farm Demo campaign; Synergies with other projects; Training modules; Digital repository for carbon & environmental models, methods & tools	Demonstration events; Report on the fifth Climate Farm Demo campaign; Synergies with other projects; Toolbox on rewarding Mechanisms; Recommendations for capacity building of advisors on climate smart farming	Practice abstracts, Final Conference Demonstration events; Report on the sixth Climate Farm Demo campaign; Synergies with other projects; Training modules; Digital repository for carbon & environmental models, methods & tools ...
Internal newsletter no.	3-4	3-4	3-4	3-4	3-4	3-4	3-4
Internal newsletter focus areas	Dissemination of all available project channels; Internal webinars and training material; Project templates tools and guidelines	Upcoming demo events / reports; WPs progress overview Deliverables submitted / upcoming deliverables	Upcoming demo events / reports; WPs progress overview Deliverables submitted / upcoming deliverables	Upcoming demo events / reports; WPs progress overview Deliverables submitted / upcoming deliverables	Upcoming demo events / reports; WPs progress overview Deliverables submitted / upcoming deliverables	Upcoming demo events / reports; WPs progress overview Deliverables submitted / upcoming deliverables	Upcoming demo events / reports; WPs progress overview Deliverables submitted / upcoming deliverables
Total number	6-8	7-9	8-10	8-10	8-10	8-10	8-10

3.5 Press Releases

A Press kit will be produced to reach national and European specialised journalists and the most relevant media to amplify CFD communication efforts and thus reach target groups not reached by other communication and dissemination activities. Press releases are also a great tool to reach a wider audience. The project will develop around 20 press releases written in English language and then, whenever relevant, these articles will be translated by partners into local languages and sent over the local and national media.

The press releases will be distributed through:

- The CFD website and social media channels,
- Partners' channels, such as websites, social media channels, email lists, agriculture related platforms,
- EU and national electronic media such as portals, platforms, blogs, but also podcasts and video shows related to agriculture and climate mitigation. I.e. CFD will share relevant press articles other relevant information with the European CAP Network to be published on their website, or included in the Newsletter targeted to Operational Groups that bring together multiple actors to advance innovation in the agricultural sector.

3.6 Editorial materials

As part of the corporate branding campaign, various editorials, branding materials and merchandise reflecting project identity will be developed throughout the project scope. A brochure for informing farmers about the project and opportunities for them has already been created (Figure 8) and translated in all 27 languages. In the following months, a general brochure promoting the project will be created together with a poster, branding elements such as a rollup banner, a flag and merchandise. These materials will be used in local context (by NCs and advisors during the farm recruiting process or by PDFs for a portion of demonstration activities), as well as in European context – conferences, fairs, synergies with other projects, etc.

Figure 8. Flyers for farmers

3.7 Multimedia Materials

Climate Farm Demo will take advantage of the already launched YouTube channel FarmDemo and it will condition its successful implementation. Under the scope of the CFD project, at least 150 high-quality videos will be produced by FiBL and other partners during the demonstration campaigns and other project events. The videos will promote good CSF practices, and they will help in sharing knowledge among farmers, advisors and other actors. All the produced videos will be published on the FarmDemo channel and further promoted on project social media channels and some of them will be issued in newsletters.

3.8 Infographics

The infographics presenting the basic information and facts about the project have been redesigned to better fit into the visual identity now that there are straightforward guidelines regarding this matter. This refers to partner information, envisaged impact, CSF solutions and more.

Figure 9. CFD infographics

Chapter 4

4. Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Channels

The present chapter shows how D&C selected channels will be managed to reach as many audiences as possible and encourage them to engage.

4.1 Climate Farm Demo Website & Online Content Repository

BIOS is developing a project website together with other partners, mainly ACTA and ILVO, but the design approach was participatory and included inputs by many partners who will be using the website for various purposes. Website contains key information about the project, shares updates through the “News” section, information about the farm demonstration events and collects all knowledge generated through the project. The website will be available in English and all local project partners' local languages. The website has been developed under Task 8.4, while the updates of the News section will be undertaken by Task 8.2. The detailed description of the website is presented in deliverable D8.3 Project website and D8.2 Online content repository (knowledge reservoir). A great potential also lies within CFD partner organisations' online presence, which is described in 4.4.

4.2 CFD Network Events

Two international conferences will be organised, bringing together the coordinators and leading partners from the two strategic projects (Climate Smart Advisors and Topic CL6 2023 CLIMATE: “Linking experimental farms”), with dedicated workshops specially intended to establish connections among the three projects. In addition to these conferences organised by CFD, the project will be presented at minimum 20 major conferences on Climate or R&I. Moreover, within WP7, meetings with other projects and initiatives that will promote project activities and results will be organised twice per year from year 3 to year 7.

4.3 Social Media

Social media has become one of the crucial ways to disseminate information and communicate with the target audience. For that reason, the CFD will be using the following platforms:

- Twitter,
- LinkedIn,
- Facebook,
- YouTube.

More about the reasoning why these platforms were chosen, social media targets, content and monitoring can be found in Chapter 5, dedicated to the social media strategy developed for CFD.

Apart from the official CFD channels, all the partners will use their profiles on various social media sites to further spread relevant information about the project which will give CFD project a potential to reach a total of over 2.7 millions of people through various social media platforms (see Table 6). The CFD project consortium includes 65 partners across Europe, which constitutes a notable network. Since the majority of the partners are widely present on social media, they are expected to repost content from the official CFD pages, as well as create their own concerning the project.

Below is a table showcasing all partners' social media profiles, their links and number of followers at the moment of writing this deliverable.

Table 6. CFD partners' social media

Short name	Legal Name	Country	Social media	Profile link	Indicative number of followers/connections
AAC/CDR	CENTRUM DORADZTWA ROLNICZEGO W BRWINOWIE	PL	Twitter	https://twitter.com/cdr_radom	147
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/in/cdr-poland-radom-42723a87/	1
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/RadomCDR	1,100
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@CDRBrwinow	8,820
ABACUS	ABACUS AGRICULTURE LIMITED	UK	Twitter	https://twitter.com/abacusagri	1,556
				https://twitter.com/Farm3Dwithtrees	3,877
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/in/ian-knight-57721064/	49
				https://www.linkedin.com/in/steve-briggs-99a22523/	275
ACTA	Association de Coordination Technique Agricole	FR	Twitter	https://twitter.com/ACTA_asso	4,222
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/acta---les-instituts-techniques-agricoles/	5,043
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/ACTA.asso/	300
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCqcs8wMgL VzdwYZ6wDTIITA	512
ADAS	RSK ADAS LIMITED	UK	Twitter	https://twitter.com/ADASGroup	7,313
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/adas/	10,635
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/ADASGroup/	769
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/c/adasukltd	114
			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/adas.uk/	1,159
AGRIDEA	AGRIDEA	CH	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/agridea/	2,999
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/agrideach/	1,200
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/user/agrideaagridea	1,160
AGROV	AGROVAST LIVSMEDEL AKTIEBOLAG	SE	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/agrov%C3%A4st-livsmedel-ab/	233
				https://www.linkedin.com/company/smartagri-digital-revolution/	376
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/gronamoten	1,300

				https://www.facebook.com/smartagridigitalrevolution	489
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCixWYRO6sbs2Hw9p8t5EkYQ/videos	115
AIA	ASSOCIAZIONE ITALIANA ALLEVATORI	IT	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/aia---associazione-italiana-allevatori/	1,234
AINTA S.L.	ASESORIA INTEGRAL AGROALIMENTARIA SL	ES	N/A	N/A	N/A
Apo Conerpo	APO CONERPO SCA	ITA	N/A	N/A	N/A
ARC	POLLUMAJANDUSUURING UTE KESKUS	EE	Twitter	https://twitter.com/123maaeluvork	N/A
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/maaeluvorgustik	1,700
				https://www.facebook.com/pollumajandusuuringutekeskus	N/A
				https://www.facebook.com/KuusikuKK	522
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/user/maainfo	571
https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCkXI5zVVHyov9e3Ddf9v2Ew	9				
ARVALIS	ARVALIS INSTITUT DU VEGETAL	FR	Twitter	https://twitter.com/arvalisofficiel	9,331
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/arvalisinstitutduvegetal/	26,763
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/arvalisinstitutduvegetal/	N/A
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/user/TVArvalis	7,030
ASOPROVA C	ASOCIACION ESPANOLA DE PRODUCTORES DE VACUNO DE CARNE	ES	Twitter	https://twitter.com/asoprovac	2,510
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/asoprovac/about/	402
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/people/ASOPROVAC-NACIONAL/100065673721889/	1,300
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCt7H8afAq2jTwYqcpKm6iWQ	363
ATB	LEIBNIZ-INSTITUT FUR AGRARTECHNIK UND BIOOKONOMIE EV	DE	Twitter	https://twitter.com/leibnizatb	1,349
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/leibnizatb/	1,463
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCSP0clb0qM-J4As6zv1FzqQ	189
AUA	GEOPONIKO PANEPISTIMION ATHINON	EL	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/sftgaua/	3,253
				https://www.linkedin.com/company/agricultural-university-of-athens/	13,992
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/AgriculturalUniversityofAthens/	6,500

			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCiRPTax6lrU8l5xY3Fie3g	658
			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/agricultural_university_athens/	2,162
BAAP	SDRUZHENIE ASOTSIATSIYA NA ZEMEDELKITE PROIZVODITELI V BULGARIYA	BG	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/people/%D0%90%D1%81%D0%BE%D1%86%D0%B8%D0%B0%D1%86%D0%B8%D1%8F-%D0%BD%D0%B0-%D0%B7%D0%B5%D0%BC%D0%B5%D0%B4%D0%B5%D0%BB%D1%81%D0%BA%D0%B8%D1%82%D0%B5-%D0%BF%D1%80%D0%BE%D0%B8%D0%B7%D0%B2%D0%BE%D0%B4%D0%B8%D1%82%D0%B5%D0%BB%D0%B8-%D0%B2-%D0%91%D1%8A%D0%BB%D0%B3%D0%B0%D1%80%D0%B8%D1%8F/100064486527058/	3,200
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCzRWIfExPKfd4rNx0K2dG3A	20
BBG	BIOLAND BERATUNG GMBH	DE	Twitter	https://twitter.com/bioland_de	11,800
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/bioland-e.-v.-verband-f%C3%BCr-organisch--biologischen-landbau/	694
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/bioland/	37,000
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@Biolandkanal	5,860
			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/bioland_official/	28,900
BEC	BIOECONOMY CLUSTER	SK	Twitter	https://twitter.com/be_cluster	24
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/bioeconomy-cluster-slovakia/	149
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/BioeconomyCluster	100
BFS	BFS / FVS	CH	N/A	N/A	N/A
BIOS	BIOSENSE INSTITUTE – RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT INSTITUTE FOR INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN BIOSYSTEMS	RS	Twitter	https://twitter.com/biosensers	2,040
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/biosense-institute/	5,425
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/biosense.institute/	2,600
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCnXEiosaHvFG4nRD4zNuDKQ	136
			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/biosense_institute/	758
CAFS	KMETIJSKO GOZDARSKA ZBORNICA SLOVENIJE	SI	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/zbornicaKGZS/	3,571
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@zbornicaKGZS	146
		FR	Twitter	https://twitter.com/ChambagriFrance	16,800

CDA France (old acronym: APCA)	ASSEMBLEE PERMANENTE DES CHAMBRES D'AGRICULTURE		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/chambres-d-agriculture-france/	40,912
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/chambres.agriculture/	17,000
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCPmthn-w8RXzJhdh7wPdgUQ/featured	1,510
			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/chambres_agriculture/	6,939
CKIC	CLIMATE-KIC HOLDING BV	NL	Twitter	https://twitter.com/ClimateKIC	43,800
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/climate-kic/	75,618
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/ClimateKIC	110,552
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@Climate-kicOrg	1,640
			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/climate.kic/	9,669
COEXPHAL	ASOCIACION DE ORGANIZACIONES DE PRODUCTORES DE FRUTAS Y HORTALIZAS DE ALMERIA	ES	Twitter	https://twitter.com/Coexphal	3,546
				https://twitter.com/aenverde	2,062
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/coexphal/	2,756
				https://www.linkedin.com/company/aenverde/	1,764
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/Coexphal/	1,100
				https://www.facebook.com/aenverde/	5,561
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/c/COEXPHALTV/videos	305
				https://www.youtube.com/@aenverde	878
Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/coexphal_/	1,178			
	https://www.instagram.com/aenverde/	1,434			
CONSULAI	CONSULAI, CONSULTORIA AGROINDUSTRIAL LDA	PT	Twitter	https://twitter.com/CONSULAI	255
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/consulai/	4,919
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/CONSULAI/	46,215
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/consulai	617
			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/consulai_pt/	1,345
CONVIS	CONVIS SOCIETE COOPERATIVE	LU	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/conviss.lu/	1,900
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@conviss.c.7521	38

CRA BFC	CHAMBRE REGIONALE D'AGRICULTURE DEBOURGOGNE-FRANCHE-COMTE	FR	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/chambre-regionale-d'agriculture-de-bourgogne-franche-comte/	846
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/ChambagriBfc	1,000
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@chambreregionaledagricultu6321	415
CRA NA	CHAMBRE REGIONALE D'AGRICULTURE NOUVELLE -AQUITAINE	FR	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/chambres-d'agriculture-nouvelle-aquitaine/	328
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@agriculturesdenouvelle-aqu4061	99
CRA PDL	CHAMBRE REGIONALE D'AGRICULTURE DES PAYS DE LA LOIRE	FR	Twitter	https://twitter.com/ChambagriPdL	3,509
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/chambre-agriculture-pays-de-la-loire/	4,863
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/Chambres.agriculture.PdL	3,200
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCB1wMulStShQ-o8eMslzgw	2,180
CRA-W	CENTRE WALLON DE RECHERCHES AGRONOMIQUES	BE	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/cra-w/	2,636
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/CRAWallonie/	5,000
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCthmSnf5CzCWGc3nyLeJvcQ/featured	506
CRAB	CHAMBRE REGIONALE D'AGRICULTURE DE BRETAGNE	FR	Twitter	https://twitter.com/chambagriBzh	5,590
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/chambres-agriculture-bretagne/	5,409
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/ChambagriBzh/	7,405
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@ChambAgriBzhvideos	2,400
CREA	CONSIGLIO PER LA RICERCA IN AGRICOLTURA E L'ANALISI DELL'ECONOMIA AGRARIA	IT	Twitter	https://twitter.com/CREARicerca	2,264
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/crea-ricerca/	23,439
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/CREARicerca/	13,000
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@CREARicercadavedere	2,790
			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/crearicerca/	2,117
CRPA	CENTRO RICERCHE PRODUZIONI ANIMALI C.R.P.A. SPA	IT	Twitter	https://twitter.com/crpa-social	265
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/centro-ricerche-produzioni-animati-scpa/	511
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCwfBQQmVqld6KvNDwSstVgg	319
CTIFL		FR	Twitter	https://twitter.com/ Ctifl	2,022

	CENTRE TECHNIQUE INTERPROFESSIONNELDES FRUITS ET LEGUMES		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ctifl/	10,446
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/user/Ctifl7	684
CZU	Česká zemědělská univerzita v Praze	CH	Twitter	https://twitter.com/CZUvPraze	2,376
				https://twitter.com/ASZ_CR	627
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/school/czuvpraze/	34,478
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/CZUvPraze/	23,000
				https://www.facebook.com/fzp.czu.cz	5,200
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/c/czu	1,310
				https://www.youtube.com/user/FZPvPraze	621
			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/czuvpraze/	8,367
https://www.instagram.com/fzp_czu/	1,391				
DRDI	DEVENISH RESEARCH DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION LIMITED	IE	Twitter	https://twitter.com/DevenishNutri	3,910
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/devenish-nutrition/	10,482
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/LandsatDowth/	969
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@DevenishNutritionLtdBelfast	90
EI	ECOLOGIC INSTITUT gemeinnützige GmbH	DE	Twitter	https://twitter.com/EcologicBerlin	8,677
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ecologic-institute-berlin-germany/	8,246
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/Ecologic.Institute	3,715
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/user/EcologicInstitute	621
EILYPS	EILYPS	FR	Twitter	https://twitter.com/eilyps	966
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/eilyps/	2,532
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/EILYPSConseilExpertiseElevage	826
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@eilyps	475
Elevéo	ELEVEO	BE	Twitter	https://twitter.com/AWEGroupe	188
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/association-wallonne-de-l%27elevation-asbl	532
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/AssociationWallonneDesEleveurs/	11,418

			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC8DY1QuRmoSrU9VUYqTnqJg	4,240
ELIANCE (old acronym: FCEL)	Eliance	FR	Twitter	https://twitter.com/Eliance_Elevage	1,890
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/eliance-elevage/	2,681
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/Elianceelevage	2,800
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCbVq5V9VXKl09ov3zVWciiA	20
ELO ASBL	EUROPEAN LANDOWNERS ORGANIZATION	BE	Twitter	https://twitter.com/eulandownersorg	3,782
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/european-landowners%27-organization/	1,725
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/europeanlandowners/	1,500
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@eloevents	142
EV ILVO	EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR LANDBOUW- EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK	BE	Twitter	https://twitter.com/ILVOvlaanderen	3,151
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ilvo/	11,212
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/InstituutVoorLandbouwEnVisserijonderzoek/	2,400
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@ILVOCOMM	531
FIBL	FORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUR BIOLOGISCHEN LANDBAU STIFTUNG	CH	Twitter	https://twitter.com/fiblorg	5,929
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/fibl/	6,312
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/FiBLnews/	7,000
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/user/FiBLFilm?feature=mhee	17,300
GLZ	GRUENLANDZENTRUM NIEDERSACHEN/BREMEN E.V.	DE	Twitter	https://twitter.com/grasslandcentre	164
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/gruenlandzentrum/	25
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/Gruenlandzentrum/	1,000
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@grunlandzentrumniedersachs7360	34
			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/gruenlandzentrum/	190
GRAND ALFRED	GRAND ALFRED	AT	Twitter	https://twitter.com/VERMIGRAND	2,449
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/in/alfred-grand-vernigrand/	500+
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/grandgarten/?locale=de_DE	1,600
			YouTube	https://youtube.com/@grandfarm3431	37

			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/grandgarten/	1,495
GSC	GREEN SUPPLY CHAIN DIGITAL INNOVATION HUB ASTIKI MI KERDOSKOPIKI ETAIREIA	EL	Twitter	https://twitter.com/GreenSupplyCha1	334
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/greensupplychain/	310
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/GreenSupplyChainDIH/	11
I4CE	I4CE - INSTITUTE FOR CLIMATE ECONOMICS	FR	Twitter	https://twitter.com/I4CE_	11,200
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/i4ce/	15,286
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/lnrae.France/	32,543
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCLZEgZVliYP6TSDrid7A3mQ	437
IBNA	INSTITUTUL NATIONAL DE CERCETAREDEZVOLTARE PENTRU BIOLOGIE SI NUTRITIE ANIMALA	RO	N/A	N/A	N/A
ICOEL	Innovationscenter for Økologisk Landbrug P/S	DK	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/innovationscenter-for-%C3%B8kologisk-landbrug/	1,713
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/icoel.dk	1,600
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UcHaRzvjDuN89idgi-2ROhyA	146
			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/derforlandmand/	3,428
IDELE	INSTITUT DE L'ELEVAGE	FR	Twitter	https://twitter.com/InstitutElevage	9,249
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/institut-de-lelevage-idele/	17,943
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/idele.fr/	11,000
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@institutdelevageidele7392	59
			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/institutelevage/	1,762
IfA	INNOVATION FOR AGRICULTURE	UK	Twitter	https://twitter.com/InnovationforAg	7,405
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/89832701/	319
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/innovationforag/	890
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC9_NAR0ykcMCMYMKFH1cYI1Q	762
IFIP	IFIP-INSTITUT DU PORC ASSOCIATION	FR	Twitter	https://twitter.com/IFIP_inst_porc	2,151
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ifip-institut-du-porc/	3,952
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCl3nOnxSPImwRwaolbZcxQA	1,390

IFJ	THE AGRICULTURAL TRUST	IE	Twitter	https://twitter.com/farmersjournal	47,100
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/farmers-journal/	13,107
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/farmers-journal/	170,602
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@IrishFarmersJournal	116,000
			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/farmersjournal/	52,400
IFOAM EU GROUP	INTERNATIONAL FEDERATION OF ORGANIC AGRICULTURE MOVEMENTS EUROPEAN UNION REGIONAL GROUP	SE	Twitter	https://twitter.com/OrganicsEurope	10,300
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/organicseurope/	11,819
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/OrganicsEurope	9,100
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/c/OrganicsEurope/	400
			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/organicseurope/	782
INNOVAL	INNOVAL SOCIETE COOPERATIVE AGRICOLE	FR	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/cooperative-innoval/	3,261
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/cooperative.innoval/	10,000
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@innoval	109
INRAE	INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE POUR L'AGRICULTURE, L'ALIMENTATION ET L'ENVIRONNEMENT	FR	Twitter	https://twitter.com/INRAE_France	46,900
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/test-science/	74,608
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/Inrae.France/	32,543
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCQxx5pTHLCoxjrr6VhLznRw	2,680
			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/inrae/	11,000
INTIA	INSTITUTO NAVARRO DE TECNOLOGIAS E INFRAESTRUCTURAS AGROALIMENTARIAS SA	ES	Twitter	https://twitter.com/IntiaSa	2,586
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/intia-sa/	1,684
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/INTIA.NAVARRA/	1,400
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@Intia_sa	736
ISP	INNOVATIESTEUNPUNT VOOR LANDBOUW ENPLATTELAND	BE	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/boerenbond/	3,867
			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/boerenbond.be/?	1,582
ITAVI	INSTITUT TECHNIQUE DE L'AVICULTURE, DE LA	FR	Twitter	https://twitter.com/ITAVIofficiel	281
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/itavi/	4,686

	CUNICULTURE ET DE LA PISCICULTUREITAVI		YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCGDWfSvRXG5VnadhMFVthQg	965
KPODR	KUJAWSKO-POMORSKI OSRODEK DORADZTWA ROLNICZEGO W MINIKOWIE	PL	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/kujawsko-pomorski-o%C5%9Brodek-doradztwa-rolniczego-w-minikowie/	7
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/kpodr/?fref=ts	5,822
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCC9bUzFo5haRN2ni9jaLz5g	1,360
			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/kpodr_w_minikowie/	854
LAAS	VIESOJI ISTAIGA LIETUVOS ZEMES UKIO KONSULTAVIMO TARNYBA	LT	Twitter	https://twitter.com/Erika_LZUKT	6
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/LZUKT/	6,959
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/user/KonsultavimoTarnyba	147
			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/konsultavimo.tarnyba/	1,120
LK Stmk	LANDESKAMMER FUER LAND UND FORTWIRTSCHAFT IN STEIERMARK	AT	YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@landwirtschaftskammersteie8713	1,760
LLKC (LRATC)	LATVIJAS LAUKU KONSULTACIJU UN IZGLITIBAS CENTRS	LT	Twitter	https://twitter.com/LLKC_lv	1,962
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/llkc/	125
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/LLKCOzolnieki	6,700
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/user/LLKCchannel	1,120
MofA	MINISTARSTVO POLJOPRIVREDE	HR	Facebook	https://hr-hr.facebook.com/Ministarstvo-poljoprivrede-331593690335587/	10,000
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCdxg3qkil7q7cneXpoYf3HA	136
NAAS	NATIONAL AGRICULTURAL ADVISORY SERVICE	BG	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/NAAS.BG/	2,000
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCRmAMkHEpzHXebBpoQspdvQ	5,820
NOKA	NATSIONALNA OVTSEVADNA I KOZEVADNAASOTSIATSIYA	BG	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/noka.bg.official	1,600
OMKI	OKOLOGIAI MEZOGAZDASAGI KUTATOINTEZET	HU	Twitter	https://twitter.com/omki_research	1,023
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/-mki-hungarian-research-institute-of-organic-agriculture/	592

	KOZHASZNU NONPROFIT KFT		Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/OMKibiokutatas/	14,000
				https://www.facebook.com/omkihungary/	732
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@omki-okologiaimezogazdasag2369	2,210
			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/omki_research_institute/	4,342
OPTIVAL – SEENORES T	OPTIVAL SOCIETE COOPERATIVE AGRICOLE	FR	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/seenorest/	332
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/Seenorest	1,200
ProAgria	PROAGRIA KESKUSTEN LIITTO RY	FI	Twitter	https://twitter.com/ProAgria	5,172
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/proagria/	4,332
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/ProAgria/	8,100
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/user/proagriavideot	640
			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/proagria/	3,733
ProAgria E-P	PROAGRIA ETELA-POHJANMAA RY	FI	Twitter	https://twitter.com/ProAgria	5,172
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/proagria/	4,332
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/ProAgria/	8,100
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/user/proagriavideot	640
			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/proagria/	3,733
RA	FUNDACION REGENERATION ACADEMY	ES	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/regeneration-academy/	2,060
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/regenerationacademy/	588
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCZvJsCjc4RDxu-GfkchMHgA/about	11
			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/regenerationacademy/	2,464
SEENOVIA	SEENOVIA	FR	Twitter	https://twitter.com/seenovia	617
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/seenovia/	2,742
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/Seenovia.conseil/	1,700
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@seenovia7425	307
SUA – SPU		SK	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/in/spunitra/	9
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/SPUNitra/	12,000

	SLOVENSKA POLNOHOSPODARSKA UNIVERZITA V NITRE		YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/user/spunitra/videos	121
			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/spunitra/	2,091
SZE	SZECHENYI ISTVAN EGYETEM	HU	Twitter	https://twitter.com/UniSze	29
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/school/unisze/	7,384
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/szeovar	2,100
				https://www.facebook.com/elelmiszertudomanyi	N/A
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@SZEgyor	1,240
			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/szechenyi.istvan.egyetem/	6,161
TEAGASC	TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY	IE	Twitter	https://twitter.com/teagasc	36,300
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/teagasc/	36,558
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/Teagasc/	452
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@TeagascMedia	14,900
			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/teagasc/	12,700
TERRES INOVIA	TERRES INOVIA	FR	Twitter	https://twitter.com/terresinovia	7,437
			LinkedIn	https://twitter.com/terresinovia	17,305
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/TerresInoviaInstitut/	2,200
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC2psktJPQ-pZaRoreuV4sAA	2,590
UAL	UNIVERSIDAD DE ALMERIA	ES	Twitter	https://twitter.com/ualmeria	39,500
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/school/universidad-de-almer-a/	40,157
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/universidaddealmeria	32,000
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCxIzAfiJt-QEP_Gxmt8AWAw	2,450
			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/unialmeria/	11,500
ULIEGE	UNIVERSITE DE LIEGE	BE	Twitter	https://twitter.com/UniversiteLiege	16,600
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/school/university-of-liege/	88,048
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/universitedeliege	52,000
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/user/universitedeliege	55,900

			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/universitedeliege/	13,600
USAMV BUCURESTI	UNIVERSITATEA DE STIINTE AGRONOMICE SI MEDICINA VETERINARA DIN BUCURESTI	RO	Twitter	https://twitter.com/USAMV_Bucuresti	53
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/school/universitatea-de-%C8%99tiin%C8%9Be-agronomice-%C8%99i-medicin%C4%83-veterinar%C4%83-din-bucure%C8%99ti/	12,590
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/usamv	18,025
			YouTube	https://www.instagram.com/usamv_buc/	2,536
			Instagram	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC4xGQ9AglqxBVuHaXG8ZDvg	853
WMODR	WARMINSKO-MAZURSKI OSRODEK DORADZTWA ROLNICZEGO Z SIEDZIBA W OLSZTYNIE	PL	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/wmodr.olsztyn	3,400
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@wmodrolsztytn5946	496
WR	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	NL	N/A	N/A	N/A
WU	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY	NL	Twitter	https://twitter.com/WUR	44,500
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/school/wageningenuniversity/	196,753
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/WUR/	40,009
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@WageningenUR	7,930
			Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/uniwageningen/	47,200
ZLTO	ZUIDELIJKE LAND- EN TUINBOUWORGANISATIE VERENIGING	NL	Twitter	https://twitter.com/ZLTO	7,599
			LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/zlto/	6,925
			Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/zltoonline	3,900
			YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCBfHeoxBcD15nd3umYIS4WA	650

Chapter 5

5. Social Media Strategy

Over the past decade, social media networks have played a major role in creating project awareness, disseminating information and engaging with relevant communities, all with the aim of boosting the promoting demonstration events, the distribution of best practices in the given sector and supporting project goals in general. This chapter describes the strategy that CFD will employ in striving towards achieving all of that.

5.1 Objectives

To ensure that the social media strategy is effective, its objectives need to be carefully crafted and ambitious yet achievable. The following goals are believed to be essential in contributing to the overall project results.

- Draw attention to the project and its scope at EU, national and local levels.
- Drive traffic to the CFD platform.
- Encourage people to subscribe to the project newsletter.
- Boost the number of views on CFD videos.
- Boost the visibility of PDFs activities.
- Support the six annual demo-campaigns.
- Disseminate best practices regarding the demo-activities to stimulate the exchange of knowledge exchange among farming actors across Europe.
- Share project results and outputs.

Focusing on more specific objectives, it is important for the strategy to achieve good communication and engagement with relevant actors throughout the project lifetime. Therefore, the aim is to:

- identify target audiences,
- tailor key messages for the different audiences on each social media platform,
- publish relevant and visually appealing content,
- create a growth hacking strategy and specify key performance indicators (KPIs),
- reach an audience outside the consortium, as well,
- monitor and evaluate the process to recognise the most fruitful efforts.

Meeting these objectives will allow for the overall CFD potential to be maximised.

5.2 Social Media Platforms

The main platforms CFD will use to connect with stakeholders and users include the social media platforms LinkedIn, Twitter and Facebook, along with the video-streaming platform YouTube. It needs to be acknowledged that the popularity of different platforms varies across regions and countries, but those mentioned here are the ones that have typically proven useful in the given context. This is supported by the findings of a survey completed by the project's NCs (described in 5.2.1).

The CFD social media accounts will be managed in English since it is a lingua franca.

5.2.1 Survey Among NCs

A short survey (available in Annex 3) was sent to all NCs to gain some insights into the use of social media by the NCs and project countries in general in relation to agriculture. This sub-chapter offers a quick overview of the responses.

To begin with, a total of 24 people filled out the questionnaire, stating their organisation and country. Asked to check all the social media sites actively used by their organisation, the NCs indicated that Facebook is the most widely used, followed by LinkedIn and Twitter, while Instagram and YouTube are less actively used by them (see figure below).

Figure 10. Social media usage reported by NCs

When it comes to the language most commonly used to publish posts on these platforms, the respondents mostly stated their local language. English was also listed, but to a notably lesser extent, as well as the combination of the local language and English.

The NCs were also asked to estimate which platform is dominant among farmers. It was somewhat expected that Facebook would rank the highest (all NCs selected as a platform used by farmers in their country), but Instagram was surprisingly estimated as more widely used than other channels. However, since the previous chart shows that the NC organisations are more present on Twitter and LinkedIn rather than Facebook, and the NCs are the CFD project’s most significant communication link with local farmers, Instagram is not deemed as an essential platform for the CFD to have its account on.

Figure 11. Estimated social media usage among farmers

Finally, when asked to provide comments, several respondents offered their opinions and remarks. For instance, one participant underlined that using several platforms is necessary to cover as many

audiences as possible. One respondent pointed out that social media is more frequently used by the younger generation, whereas the average age of farmers in their country is over 50. To conclude, the CFD D&C team has decided to offer content through Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook and YouTube, in addition to the official project website (which is not described in this document since there is a separate deliverable dedicated to it). More details about said platforms is available in the following sub-chapters.

5.2.2 Twitter

The Twitter account @ClimateFarmDemo has been created to share short yet informative content. Considering that the project is still at an early stage at the moment of submitting this deliverable, the number of followers and their engagement are expected to report a more notable increase with time.

The account will be utilised to share project activities and results, as well as topics and notions related to the CFD essence and thematic areas. Moreover, it is necessary to regularly:

- check the homepage and potentially retweet content related to CFD,
- monitor the inbox and respond to direct messages, if possible,
- reply to comment and mentions,
- check new followers and follow back if appropriate.

Figure 12. CFD Twitter account

5.2.3 LinkedIn

The project uses a LinkedIn account (www.linkedin.com/company/climatefarmdemo/) to reach more diverse target audiences by mirroring the most relevant updates on the CFD website, sharing industry news, placing spotlight on networking opportunities for farmers, and more.

To ensure proper communication and maximum effectiveness, it is necessary to regularly:

- check the homepage and potentially repost content related to CFD.
- reply to comments and direct messages.
- check new followers and follow back if appropriate.
- establish connections with relevant people/organisations.

Figure 13. CFD LinkedIn account

5.2.4 Facebook

A Facebook page bearing the project name (<https://www.facebook.com/climatefarmdemo>) has been created later compared to the Twitter and LinkedIn accounts after gaining insight into NCs' estimation about farmers' use of social media in their respective countries (presented earlier in this chapter). Therefore, although not originally planned, the CFD team decided to launch a Facebook page primarily as a supporting channel that will allow partner organisations to repost relevant content and add commentary in their local languages so that the farming community can see it.

Figure 14. CFD Facebook page

5.2.5 YouTube

All videos created by the project will be uploaded to the FarmDemo channel on YouTube, used by the RUR-11 projects PLAID, AgriDemo F2F, and NEFERTITI. This means an additional boost for the potential of CFD videos since the channel is already well-established, with around 1,640 subscribers. Therefore, new video material is likely to gain much more attention than it would had there been a separate, new channel launched.

The CFD videos will be further shared on other social media channels (Twitter and LinkedIn) since it is a great way to attract more viewers. These will be lecture-style videos (tutorials) to boost the impact in terms of key findings. Wherever possible, the content will be produced in local languages, with subtitles in selected partner languages. To additionally accelerate the dissemination of such videos, CFD partner should promote them on their national web-platforms and social media accounts.

NEFERTITI Achievements & Impacts
571 views · 10 months ago
This video summarizes and reflects on selected highlights and achievements of the NEFERTITI project.

Figure 15. FarmDemo YouTube channel

5.3 Target Audiences on Social Media & Key Messages

The CFD project aspires to reach several different kinds of target audiences via social media. The following table shows the main purpose of posts for each group and key messages.

Table 7. Target audiences and key messages

Farmers	
Purpose/Impact	To ensure that farmers and relevant AKIS sectors are connected; to boost peer-to-peer learning; to raise the farming community's awareness of CSF practices and rewarding mechanisms
Key message(s)	Farms can become more sustainable through the implementation of CSF measures. Innovative knowledge can be acquired through national and EU networks of PDFs. Innovative tools and expert advice tailored for specific farmer needs can reduce climate impact. Farmers can be rewarded for implementing CSF practices.
Agriculture advisory services	
Purpose/Impact	To enhance advisors' capacity to support farmers; to strengthen advisors' key role in regional and national CS-AKIS; to expand the network through dissemination channels.
Key message(s)	Agriculture advisors can provide better advice to farmers by benefitting from innovative tools and undergoing training related to CSF. Advisors can also benefit from participating in national and EU multi-actor networks offering knowledge exchange and encouraging the creation of new solutions.
Economic actors of the supply chain	
Purpose/Impact	To better comprehend farmer needs and challenges and improve their services; to accelerate the potential of the carbon market; to expand the network.
Key message(s)	Economic actors of the supply chain should take part in farmers networks and connect with different actors and stakeholders in the national AKIS; farmers should be rewarded for their capacity to make their production more climate neutral.
Research & Education	
Purpose/Impact	To boost partnerships that accelerate the creation of CSF practices; to raise students' awareness about the farming sector's capacity concerning sustainable land management.
Key message(s)	The research & education sector should work with different stakeholders engaged in sustainable transitions; the sector should impart knowledge on new generations in terms of the role of sustainable farming practices.
EIP-AGRI Service Point & CAP Networks	
Purpose/Impact	To reach engage with a wide network of relevant stakeholder groups in the cross-fertilisation; to have this audience use their dissemination channels to expand the network.
Key message(s)	This group can advance knowledge exchange among the project and other AKIS actors and share information about relevant solutions, methods and tools, while also stimulating innovation partnerships in the European and national AKIS
Policy makers	
Purpose/Impact	To create and promote new policy incentives accelerating farmer engagement in CSF; to fund subsequent CSF projects in order to reach the goals of the EU Climate strategy.
Key message(s)	Policy makers can gain evidence of the advantages and effectiveness of CSF in adapting to climate change.
Consumers & citizens	
Purpose/Impact	To inform citizens and steer them toward habits and attitudes aligned with sustainable transition targets, to connect consumers with National AKIS.
Key message(s)	Citizens can benefit if they learn more about the potential of the farming sector to reduce GHG emissions and increase carbon sequestration; this will also encourage citizens and consumers to support sustainable production.

5.4 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Setting ambitious yet meaningful KPIs is essential for maximising the contribution of the social media strategy to the overall project goals. The table below presents the KPIs, current values and targets that should be reached at the end of the project (M84).

Table 8. Social media KPIs

KPI	Current value	Target (M84)
N° of posts on Twitter	34	1,000
N° of followers on Twitter	88	2,000
N° of posts on LinkedIn	31	670
N° of followers on LinkedIn	206	1,200
N° of posts on Facebook	-	500
N° of followers on Facebook	-	1000
N° of videos posted on YouTube	-	150
N° of subscribers on YouTube	1,650	2,300
N° of YouTube videos views	-	75 000
Total reach on social media	-	500,000

5.5 Content Strategy

5.5.1 Defining Content

The content will be shared in formats that are in line with the needs of the farming community, as it is the main target group, while also considering their country and sector. This includes:

- easy-to-read text posts,
- pictures, infographics, illustrations, etc. with relevant content,
- videos.

Any member of the CFD consortium can share information to post on social media. If they have information about events, papers/articles or other materials that can be included in the content calendar, they should email milica.lukic@biosense.rs or dajana@vujaklija@biosense.rs.

In addition, any member of the consortium may share social media posts on their organisation's channels, ensuring that CFD is tagged and appropriate hashtags used (see 5.5.4). It should be emphasised that certain content could be confidential or sensitive in other ways, so this must be considered to avoid causing any kind of shocks or discomfort.

5.5.2 Growth Hacking Strategy

Aiming to expand the CFD social media following, the growth hacking approach will be employed since it entails marketing and promotional techniques focused on efficient and rapid growth to achieve long-term end-user sustainability. As a result, the content will be carefully prepared, and the project will gain the status of a reliable and educative knowledge reservoir. To ensure that this content reaches as many

people as possible, all CFD partners will be encouraged to recommend it in their professional circles by inviting followers, sharing, liking, and commenting.

The main steps should, therefore, be to:

1. carefully tailor content considered appropriate for each of the audiences of the social media platforms used,
2. monitor the performance of the platforms in the early stage of the project and set reasonable targets for the rest of the project lifetime,
3. test the approach by experimenting with formatting styles, posting content at different times of the day, etc.,
4. analyse the performance by monitoring analytics using tools designed for that,
5. assess the analytics at regular team meetings to draw conclusions about which posts are the most well-received and engaging and what changes are necessary to improve the results.

5.5.3 Content Calendar & Translations

A social media calendar will be created in the project's online workspace (MS Teams) to ensure that content on social media is generated in an organised and effective way, as well as to provide a neat overview. That includes a monthly content calendar of the CFD social media. As the WP8 leader, BIOS will design the calendar containing information such as date, topic, message, platform, post link and more.

Based on content relevance to a specific region, designated partners will translate and post the content on their respective social media channels. This does not include certain posts that cannot be available in advance due to their nature (for instance, live-tweeting from meetings, field visits, etc.)

5.5.4 Practical Tips & Suggested Hashtag List

This sub-chapter offers several practical tips that refer to both the C&D team and CFD partners in general.

- Be consistent, but do not resort to repetitive or irrelevant posts if there is a lack of new content.
- Strive to publish grammatically correct and properly formatted posts.
- Keep the tone and language neutral (neither too professional nor too informal), without sounding too technical.
- Share posts on all of your social media channels, if appropriate.
- Engage with your community by responding to comments and direct messages when possible.

As for suggested hashtags, the main one that should be featured in project-related posts is #ClimateFarmDemo (alternatively #CFD if remaining character number does not allow for the longer version). In addition, the following hashtags should be used when appropriate:

- #FarmDemo
- #HorizonEU
- #SmartFarming
- #ClimateAdaptation
- #ClimateChange
- #ClimateAction
- #ClimateNeutrality
- #EUfunding

- #EuGreenDeal
- #GHG
- #AKIS
- #AgrilInnovations
- #Sustainability

Other hashtags can be added if necessary. For example, partners may use hashtags in their own language or in connection to particular events.

- #EUconference
- #Paris
- #Dublin
- etc.

5.6 Monitoring & Evaluation

To ensure that all the objectives and targets are met, WP8 will use an internal document to track the following:

- number of posts on each platform,
- type of post (textual, image or video),
- date of posting,
- subject,
- number of likes,
- number of shares/retweets,
- number of comments,
- impressions,
- reach,
- total engagement.
- number of followers on each platform at the end of each month.

This will be discussed regularly at team meetings.

Chapter 6

6. Dissemination and Exploitation of Project Results

The chapter below offers an insight into how all the knowledge and results accumulated throughout the project will be gathered, disseminated and exploited.

Dissemination activities encompass all efforts made in sharing knowledge and other results generated during the project towards specific stakeholders, while exploitation activities utilise project findings and results in further research/networking activities beyond the current project. CFD will enable efficient, targeted and impact orientated planning for dissemination and exploitation of the project results, including effective knowledge transfer.

All knowledge generated and all results achieved during the project will be collected, disseminated and exploited in accordance with the Consortium Agreement signed by all project partners and by respecting defined Intellectual Property Rights. The main aims of dissemination and exploitation activities is to: i) promote accessibility of outputs and results of the project to identified stakeholders, ii) identify exploitable KERs and their target users, iii) boost the uptake of project results.

Activities that support dissemination and exploitation of project results and findings are 1) the constant update of Online knowledge repository with Open Access, 2) developing policy briefs and translation all EU languages, 3) online knowledge sharing platform for Open Access, 4) direct engagement and knowledge sharing activities with project partners and other stakeholders such as webinars, workshops, trainings, farm demonstrations (WP3), field days, conferences etc; 5) activities that supports synergies with other projects and initiatives that could benefit from the results developed under CFD (WP7).

Table 9. Key Exploitable Results (KER)

KER	KPI	DUE DATE	Target audience
Climate Farm demo training toolbox	1 – training toolbox available on the Platform	M80	Farmers, advisors
Digital repository for carbon & environmental models, methods & tools	3	M18, M48, M78	Farmers, advisors
EIP-AGRI Practice Abstracts	300	M12, M48, M72	EIP-AGRI Service Point & CAP Networks
Policy briefs	Sets of policy briefs for: i) scaling CSF rewarding mechanisms, ii) policy links at EU, regional and national level	M72, M78	Policy makers
Harmonised MRV framework and guidelines	1	M36	Policy makers, farmers, research & education
Adaptation & Mitigation Measures guidebooks on 12 thematic areas	2 x 27 languages		EIP-AGRI Service Point & CAP Networks, farmers, advisors, policy makers
A guidebook for rewarding mechanisms	27	M60	Farmers, policy makers
Online Knowledge Repository	1	M6-M84	Farmers, Advisors, Policy makers, research & education
High-quality videos	150	M12-M84	Farmers, advisors, research & education

WP8 will work closely with other WPs in order to identify the best strategies to exploit project results to maximise the impact of Climate Farm Demo project. This will be undertaken through online meetings and exploitation workshops linked to project meetings. The DEC monitoring system will ensure constant recording and monitoring of all KERs, while custom made exploitation strategy for each KER will be presented in the first revision of the DEC plan (M26).

Chapter 7

7. DEC Plans on National Level

This segment will inform the reader about the importance of national C&D, its main aspects and activities and the purpose and structure of DEC plans on national level.

Since CFD aims at activating and engaging local stakeholders across Europe, national communication and dissemination efforts are on the top of priorities for WP8. National coordinators will target and commit all relevant national AKIS actors and use all proper national communication and dissemination channels. To do so, the NCs will be trained and encouraged to use different networks, including but not limited to national AKIS, CAP Networks in their day-to-daywork, as well as their own or third-party websites, social media channels or newsletters. National DEC activities will be undertaken within Task 8.3, with inputs from T8.1 and T8.2.

There are four main aspects of national communication: (i) promotion of project, its activities, ambition, opportunities and benefits for local community, (ii) promotion of farm demo events and good examples of CSF practices, (iii) promotion of supporting activities and capacity building opportunities, and (iv) dissemination and exploitation of project results. For national communication activities it is important to identify what type of activities should take place in order to inform local and national stakeholders about the project and what activities could encourage their engagement in project activities.

The NCs will, together with communication officers from all partner organisations from specific countries, develop annual DEC plans on national level (Annex 4). The purpose of these plans is to enable strategic planning of DEC activities, contextualise the strategy depending on available and most relevant communication channels, habits and communication needs of local communities, but also to enable easy and fluent reporting on DEC activities performed and at the same time enable modifying the plan for upcoming year based on results achieved in previous period.

▲ Public relations / activities towards thematic or general media

Table 3. Mapping of relevant magazines, newspapers, internet portals, TV or radio shows, podcasts etc

Media	Link (if applicable)	Brief description	Potential reach
Raw txt			

Figure 16. Segment from the Annual DEC plan on national level template

DEC plans on national level contain following chapters:

- Report on C&D activities in previous period,
- Main DEC objectives for the upcoming period,
- Digital communication/dissemination activities,

- Public relations / activities towards thematic or general media (including the mapping of all relevant media and listing the planned activities),
- Organisation or participation in events (both online and physical),
- Linking with projects, initiatives or policy makers on local, national or regional level (connection to WP7),
- Print material
- Other communication, dissemination or exploitation activities.

For each of these activities, there is table that indicating the description of the activity, target audience, partners involved and the due date. Moreover, Annual plans also serve to help NCs to request what they need from other partners to be able to smoothly carry on all DEC activities. Therefore, for each DEC activity type, there is the additional table for requests from other partners that indicates what is needed, from whom and by when.

Table 4. List of PR activities

No	Topic of press release article	Media (list all web portals, TV or radio channels, etc you want to reach)	Due date
1	Raw txt		
2			
...			

Table 5. contribution/inputs needed from WP8, other WPs or specific partners for PR activities

No. of the activity from the above table	Contribution needed (i.e. Specific information, template, text, visual, specific input...)	Partner or Work Package Assigned	Due date
1.	Raw txt		
2.			
3.			
4.			
...			

Figure 17. Segment from Annual DEC plan on national level template: how national coordinators will use the annual plans for i) planning of DEC activities and ii) requesting material and inputs from other partners

Chapter 8

8. Monitoring & Evaluation

The main focus is the management of DEC activities, looking at the tasks of WP8 and Communication Officers appointed by each partner. This chapter also presents all the deliverables and milestones pertaining to WP8, the monitoring system and result indicators.

8.1 Management of DEC activities

Successful DEC initiatives require close collaboration among WP8, other WPs and NCs, which will boost communication and dissemination efforts on national level. Therefore, by having a clear plan and working closely with different tasks leaders, consortium partners and all project stakeholders, WP8 will ensure the achievement of all objectives and ensure the project has a lasting impact on the wider community. The next section describes the tasks under WP8, its interrelations and interrelations between WP8 and other WPs.

WP 8 - Dissemination, Exploitation and communication will manage all DEC activities on both European scale and on national level. The work package is led by BioSense Institute with the support of Deputy work package leader – Irish Farm Journal (IFJ).

The roles of WP8 leader are the following:

- Plan and coordinate implementation of all DEC activities,
- Manage the news and events on the website,
- Manage project official social media accounts,
- Manage development, creation and distribution of project newsletters and press releases,
- Report on DEC activities, compiling information received by the partners.

Each partner appointed Communication Officers (Table 10), who will:

- Create annual DEC plans and reports on DEC activities,
- Produce the DEC material in local language (translate the English version of relevant content, adopt it to local context if needed, and/or develop additional material for purpose of DEC activities on national level),
- Translate and adapt press releases and distribute towards local and national media,
- Ensure the project gain the satisfying local/national coverage, target and reach relevant stakeholders,
- Ensure all relevant project results are disseminated towards relevant national and local stakeholders.

Task 8.1: Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (M1-M84)

Task Leader: BIOS; Partners: CONSULAI, IFJ, IDELE, ACTA, All National Coordinators

The Deliverable 8.1 is developed under this task, and it will be updated every 2 years to reflect all changes, new opportunities and new synergies. This task will also monitor all DEC activities performed under the project, and it will ensure close collaboration between WP8 and WP7 Linking and coordinating with other projects, initiatives and policymakers (PIPs)

Task 8.2: Dissemination and communication activities at project level (M3-M84)

Task Leader: BIOS; Partners: CONS, IFJ, ACTA, IDELE, FIBL, IFOAM EU, ELO, GRAND ALFRED, DRDI, RA

Following DEC plan, this task will be responsible for developing all DEC tools and materials as well as managing communication channels such as social media accounts, project newsletters and press releases. All visual material, including visual identity of the project, graphic materials, print and digital

materials and multimedia will also be developed under this task, answering the needs of all other work packages and other WP8 tasks.

Task 8.3: Communication and dissemination at National level (M3-M84)

Task Leader: IFJ ; Partners: All partners

This task will ensure effective communication on national level. Annual DEC plans on national level will help in coordinated and effectively monitored DEC activities in all countries. Besides regular DEC activities designed to reach national and local stakeholders, this task will ensure collaboration with PIPs on national level, according to the plans developed under WP7.

Task 8.4: Online knowledge reservoir (M1-M84)

Task Leader: BIOS; Partners: All NCs

Besides basic project content and news/articles for the website produced under T8.2, the website will act as a knowledge reservoir for the bulk of project results and outcomes. The website will contain a comprehensive inventory of demonstration farms and farm demonstration events organised across Europe. The knowledge reservoir will also serve as an online link between the project and other knowledge repositories and knowledge sources such as Farmbook.

Task 8.5: Climate Farm Demo final training toolbox (M24-M84)

Lead: IDELE; Partners: CONSULAI, IFJ, BIOS

This task will capitalise on all training modules developed across the other to make it available for a wide audience at EU & international scales. All training modules and contents will be fine-tuned in e-learning or physical training courses and made available on the project platform (T8.4) and at national levels (T8.3).

To ensure smooth cooperation with the partners, each organisation was asked to appoint a communication officer. The table below lists each partner organisation's communication contact.

Table 10. Partner organisations' communication officers

Short name	Legal name	Country	Communication officer
AAC/CDR	CENTRUM DORADZTWA ROLNICZEGO W BRWINOWIE	PL	Mateusz Sekowski
ABACUS	ABACUS AGRICULTURE LIMITED	UK	Ian Knight
ACTA	ASSOCIATION DE COORDINATION TECHNIQUE AGRICOLE	FR	Aurore Gilet
ADAS	RSK ADAS LIMITED	UK	Brid Cooney
AGRIDEA	AGRIDEA	CH	Azra Abidovic; Pascal Python
AGROV	AGROVAST LIVSMEDEL AKTIEBOLAG	SE	Charlotta Wångdahl
AIA	ASSOCIAZIONE ITALIANA ALLEVATORI	IT	Riccardo Negrini
AINTA S.L.	ASESORIA INTEGRAL AGROALIMENTARIA SL	ES	Tamara Muñoz
Apo Conerpo	APO CONERPO SCA	ITA	Marco Giacomoni
ARC	POLLUMAJANDUSUURINGUTE KESKUS	EE	Hanna Tamsalu
ARVALIS	ARVALIS INSTITUT DU VEGETAL	FR	Maureen STADEL
ASOPROVAC	ASOCIACION ESPANOLA DE PRODUCTORES DE VACUNO DE CARNE	ES	Lucía Díez
ATB	LEIBNIZ-INSTITUT FÜR AGRARTECHNIK UND BIOÖKONOMIE EV	DE	Ulrike Glaubitz
AUA	GEOPONIKO PANEPISTIMION ATHINON	EL	Vasilis Psiroukis
BAAP	SDRUZHENIE ASOTSIATSIYA NA ZEMEDELSKITE PROIZVODITELI V BULGARIYA	BG	Teodora Georgieva
BBG	BIOLAND BERATUNG GMBH	DE	Sigrid Griese
BEC	BIOECONOMY CLUSTER	SK	Dana Simova
BFS	BFS / FVS	CH	Pascal Python
BIOS	BIOSENSE INSTITUTE – RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT INSTITUTE FOR INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN BIOSYSTEMS	RS	Milica Lukić
CAFS	KMETIJSKO GOZDARSKA ZBORNICA SLOVENIJE	SI	Igor Hrovatič
CDA France (old acronym: APCA)	CHAMBRES D'AGRICULTURE FRANCE	FR	Sylvain Sturel
CKIC	CLIMATE-KIC HOLDING BV	NL	Laurene Lebelt
COEXPHAL	ASOCIACION DE ORGANIZACIONES DE PRODUCTORES DE FRUTAS Y HORTALIZAS DE ALMERIA	ES	Eduardo Crisol-Martínez
CONSULAI	CONSULAI, CONSULTORIA AGROINDUSTRIAL LDA	PT	Maria Mendonça
CONVIS	CONVIS SOCIETE COOPERATIVE	LU	Rocco Liroy
CRA BFC	CHAMBRE REGIONALE D'AGRICULTURE DE BOURGOGNE-FRANCHE-COMTE	FR	Delphine Fouchard
CRA NA	CHAMBRE REGIONALE D'AGRICULTURE NOUVELLE -AQUITAINE	FR	Marie FERRAGUT
CRA PDL	CHAMBRE REGIONALE D'AGRICULTURE DES PAYS DE LA LOIRE	FR	Laura Perez
CRA-W	CENTRE WALLON DE RECHERCHES AGRONOMIQUES	BE	Geneviève Minne
CRAB	CHAMBRE REGIONALE D'AGRICULTURE DE BRETAGNE	FR	Elisabeth Colnard

CREA	CONSIGLIO PER LA RICERCA IN AGRICOLTURA E L'ANALISI DELL'ECONOMIA AGRARIA	IT	Sara Carè
CRPA	CENTRO RICERCHE PRODUZIONI ANIMALI C.R.P.A. SPA	IT	Andrea Porcelluzzi
CTIFL	CENTRE TECHNIQUE INTERPROFESSIONNEL DES FRUITS ET LEGUMES	FR	Jean-Marc Goachet; Ariane Grisey
CZU	Česká zemědělská univerzita v Praze	CH	TBC
DRDI	DEVENISH RESEARCH DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION LIMITED	IE	Jean Kennedy
EI	ECOLOGIC INSTITUT gemeinnützige GmbH	DE	Ilka Merbold
EILYPS	EILYPS	FR	Mélanie Vaultier
Elevéo	ELEVEO	BE	Edouard Reding
ELO ASBL	EUROPEAN LANDOWNERS ORGANIZATION	BE	Anna De Boeck
EV ILVO	EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR LANDBOUW- EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK	BE	Laure Triste
ELIANCE (old acronym: FCEL)	ELIANCE	FR	Nicolas Gaudilliere
FIBL	FORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUR BIOLOGISCHEN LANDBAU STIFTUNG	CH	Seraina Siragna
GLZ	GRUENLANDZENTRUM NIEDERSACHEN/BREMEN E.V.	DE	Siw Fasting
GRAND ALFRED	GRAND ALFRED	AT	Alfred Grand
GSC	GREEN SUPPLY CHAIN DIGITAL INNOVATION HUB ASTIKI MI KERDOSKOPIKI ETAIREIA	EL	Katerina Giagiakou
I4CE	I4CE - INSTITUTE FOR CLIMATE ECONOMICS	FR	Claudine Foucherot
IBNA	INSTITUTUL NATIONAL DE CERCETAREDEZVOLTARE PENTRU BIOLOGIE SI NUTRITIE ANIMALA	RO	Gabriela Cornescu
ICOEL	Innovationscenter for Økologisk Landbrug P/S	DK	Maria Alejandra Arias Escobar
IDELE	INSTITUT DE L'ELEVAGE	FR	Christine Berger
IfA	INNOVATION FOR AGRICULTURE	UK	Natasha Smith
IFIP	IFIP-INSTITUT DU PORC ASSOCIATION	FR	Claude Montariol
IFJ	THE AGRICULTURAL TRUST	IE	Ellen Durkin
IFOAM EU GROUP	INTERNATIONAL FEDERATION OF ORGANIC AGRICULTURE MOVEMENTS EUROPEAN UNION REGIONAL GROUP	SE	Anna Tuzzato
INNOVAL	INNOVAL SOCIETE COOPERATIVE AGRICOLE	FR	Martial Busuttil
INRAE	INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE POUR L'AGRICULTURE, L'ALIMENTATION ET L'ENVIRONNEMENT	FR	Armelle Perennes
INTIA	INSTITUTO NAVARRO DE TECNOLOGIAS E INFRAESTRUCTURAS AGROALIMENTARIAS SA	ES	Isabel Gárriz
ISP	INNOVATIESTEUNPUNT VOOR LANDBOUW ENPLATTELAND	BE	Bieke Bockx
ITAVI	INSTITUT TECHNIQUE DE L'AVICULTURE, DE LA CUNICULTURE ET DE LA PISCICULTURE - ITAVI	FR	Vincent Blazy; Anne Plantie-Roux
KPODR	KUJAWSKO-POMORSKI OSRODEK DORADZTWA ROLNICZEGO W MINIKOWIE	PL	Dawid Skotnicki
LAAS	VIESOJI ISTAIGA LIETUVOS ZEMES UKIO KONSULTAVIMO TARNYBA	LT	Lina Žukauskienė

LK Strmk	LANDESKAMMER FUER LAND UND FORTWIRTSCHAFT IN STEIERMARK	AT	Heike Grössing
LLKC (LRATC)	LATVIJAS LAUKU KONSULTACIJU UN IZGLITIBAS CENTRS	LT	Silvija Dreijere
MofA	MINISTARSTVO POLJOPRIVREDE	HR	Zlatko Tomljanović
NAAS	NATIONAL AGRICULTURAL ADVISORY SERVICE	BG	Dimitar Vanev
NOKA	NATSIONALNA OVTSEVADNA I KOZEVADNAASOTSIATSIYA	BG	Simeon Karakolev
OMKI	OKOLOGIAI MEZOGAZDASAGI KUTATOINTEZET KOZHASZNU NONPROFIT KFT	HU	Petra Almási
OPTIVAL – SEENOREST	OPTIVAL SOCIETE COOPERATIVE AGRICOLE	FR	Nadège Godfroy
ProAgria	PROAGRIA KESKUSTEN LIITTO RY	FI	Maria Suomela
ProAgria E-P	PROAGRIA ETELA-POHJANMAA RY	FI	Henna Latvala
RA	FUNDACION REGENERATION ACADEMY	ES	Rodrigo Vargas
SEENOVIA	SEENOVIA	FR	Marine Tessier
SUA	SLOVENSKA POLNOHOSPODARSKA UNIVERZITA V NITRE	SK	Danka Moravcikova
SZE	SZECHENYI ISTVAN EGYETEM	HU	András Vér
TEAGASC	TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY	IE	Tom O'Dwyer
TERRES INOVIA	TERRES INOVIA	FR	Francis Flénet
UAL	UNIVERSIDAD DE ALMERIA	ES	Rosa María Heredia Hortigüela
ULIEGE	UNIVERSITE DE LIEGE	BE	Jérôme Eeckhout
USAMV BUCURESTI	UNIVERSITATEA DE STIINTE AGRONOMICE SI MEDICINA VETERINARA DIN BUCURESTI	RO	Adrian Asanica; Alexandra Cornea
WMODR	WARMINSKO-MAZURSKI OSRODEK DORADZTWA ROLNICZEGO Z SIEDZIBA W OLSZTYNIE	PL	Bartosz Kubaski
WR	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	NL	Serguei Markovic
WU	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY	NL	Mariana Debernardini
ZLTO	ZUIDELIJKE LAND- EN TUINBOUWORGANISATIE VERENIGING	NL	Aniek de Jong

8.2 DEC Monitoring System

8.2.1 List of WP8 Deliverables and Milestones

The following two tables contain all the deliverables and milestones that WP8 is in charge of.

Table 11. WP8 deliverables

Deliverable No.	Deliverable name	Lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemination level	Due date (month)
D8.1	Dissemination, exploitation & communication Plan at EU & National levels	BIOS	R — Document, report	PU – Public	6
D8.2	Online content repository (knowledge reservoir)	BIOS	DEC —Websites, patent filings, videos, etc	PU – Public	6
D8.3	Project website	BIOS	DEC —Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.	PU – Public	6
D8.4	First report on digital and printed dissemination, exploitation and communication material	BIOS	R — Document, report	PU – Public	12
D8.5	EIP practice abstracts - batch 1	BIOS	R — Document, report	PU – Public	12
D8.6	Dissemination, exploitation & communication Plan at EU & National levels - First revision	BIOS	R — Document, report	PU – Public	26
D8.7	EIP practice abstracts - batch 2	BIOS	R — Document, report	PU – Public	48
D8.8	Dissemination, exploitation & communication Plan at EU & National levels - Second revision	BIOS	R — Document, report	PU – Public	50
D8.9	EIP practice abstracts - batch 3	BIOS	R — Document, report	PU – Public	72
D8.10	Climate Farm Demo final training toolbox	BIOS	DEC —Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.	PU – Public	80
D8.11	Final report on digital and printed dissemination, exploitation and communication material	BIOS	R — Document, report	PU – Public	84
D8.12	Updated online content repository (knowledge reservoir)	BIOS	DEC —Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.	PU – Public	84

Table 12. WP8 Milestones

Milestone No.	Milestone name	Lead beneficiary	Means of verification	Due date (month)
74	Website is online and operational	BIOS	Website link working	6
75	Infographics	BIOS	Publication on the website	6

76	Graphic Standards Manual (Visual identity, guidelines)	BIOS	Document shared	6
----	--	------	-----------------	---

8.2.2 Monitoring system

For constant monitoring of DEC activities, various tools will be adopted:

- Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Reporting Table shared on shared collaborative repository available to all partners,
- DEC quarterly meetings between the WP8 members and all national communication officers,
- Annual plans and reports.

Figure 18. Relation between planning, executing and reporting on DEC activities

Annual national plans will be created to ensure strategic approach in DEC activities even on a national level. Each Annual plan will also contain one part with a report on all activities undertaken during the previous period. However, reporting will not only rely on reports delivered once each year. Instead, all partners will be encouraged and frequently reminded to regularly update the DEC reporting table which contains a comprehensive information about each DEC activity, such as mapping of stakeholders reached (not only the primary audience, but also people who were not targeted but were reached by the performed activity), general information such as when, where, how the activity happen and by whom, and finally it contains information relevant for WP7 – whether the activity was organised together with other projects. Besides the DEC reporting table, National Communication Officers are invited to quarterly meetings to discuss about what we achieved so far and our next steps.

8.2.3. Result Indicators

Table 13. CFD result indicators

Indicator	Value
N° of Pilot Demo Farms	1500
N° of Demonstration activities	4500
N° of Official project newsletters	56
N° of subscribers for the newsletter	400
N° of Climate Farm Demo website visitors	14 000
N° of posts across all CFD social media channels	2 170
N° of followers across all CFD social media channels	4 200
Total reach on CFD social media channels	500 000
N° of Training modules	5
N° of Training sessions	200
N° of International Conferences	2
N° of participants at international conferences	400
N° of policy briefs	5
N° of EIP-AGRI Practice Abstracts	300
N° of press articles	20
N° of media outlets	400
N° of participation in EU-scale events	20
N° of EU AKIS actors directly reached by Climate Farm Demo practices, methods, tools and trainings	250 000
N° of farmers reached by demo activities and engaged in CSF practices	150 000
N° of advisors using the training modules, methods and tools to support farmers	1000
N° of farmers and advisory networks participating in Climate Farm Demo activities	500
N° of CFD videos on the YouTube FarmDemo channel	150
N° of YouTube videos views	75 000
N° of articles published by partners	300

Chapter 9

9. Conclusions

This is to summarise the main conclusions drawn after carefully analysing and designing everything that the DEC plan contains to achieve its goals and support the objectives of the CFD project in general.

Deliverable 8.1 Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication Plan at EU & National Levels, as the first version of the Plan, aims to describe strategies, tools and channels that will be used in the Climate Farm Demo project to meet various DEC objectives. It is a rather extensive document since its main purpose is to present the actions and approaches considered the most useful in promoting project activities, disseminating results, exploiting knowledge and solutions coming from the project and raising awareness of the benefits of CSF and the significance of climate neutrality. This will be accomplished through the use of the CFD website, social media platforms, newsletters and other tools and channels considered suitable.

The expected results are numerous and can be reflected in quantified targets such as the number of PDFs, demo activities, social media followers, YouTube video views, press articles, EIP-AGRI practice abstracts, training sessions and more. Since some time is typically needed to test approaches like these to ensure the maximum effectiveness, this deliverable, submitted in M6, will be revised and updated in M26 and M50 to potentially expand it and/or make alterations to certain segments if necessary. This is important because data from analytic tools can indicate what works best (which tools are the most useful, what social media posts attract the most attention and so forth), although this information may not always clearly point towards the reason why certain approach is or is not sufficiently effective. Therefore, the basis for the DEC revisions will be the regular monitoring & evaluation process led by BIOS as the WP8 with the support of all project partners, with special focus on Communication Officers appointed by each partner organisation. For that reason, this document also offers guidelines and practical tips for all the consortium members since essentially all parties are expected to contribute to the DEC goals.

To conclude, a well-managed and functional DEC approach is necessary for the success of CFD. Thanks to the DEC, WP8 and the rest of the consortium will be able to follow the Plan, and it will maximise the potential of their efforts to reach existing and new audiences and thus also amplify the potential to achieve real impact that is necessary in order to contribute to the objectives of EU Climate strategy.

Chapter 10

10. Annexes

Below are all the annexes mentioned previously in the document.

Annex 1: CFD Corporate Identity Manual

Climate Farm Demo

A EUROPEAN-WIDE NETWORK OF PILOT FARMERS
IMPLEMENTING AND DEMONSTRATING CLIMATE SMART
SOLUTIONS FOR A CARBON NEUTRAL EUROPE

Corporate Identity Manual

Climate Farm Demo – Corporate Identity Manual

Index

1. The Logo
2. Corporate Colours
3. Typography and Font
4. Logo Size
5. Logo Protection Zone
6. Logo Versions
7. Logo Over an Image or Photo
8. Examples of Bad Logo Usage

1. The Logo

The Climate Farm Demo project aims to strengthen European farmers' capacities to implement, demonstrate and uptake Climate Smart Farming practice across the EU. That involves a network of 1,500 Pilot Demo Farmers and Climate Farm Advisors from 28 countries, different agricultural sectors and Adaptation & Mitigation thematic areas, accelerating the knowledge exchanges and capacity building. The circular shape of the logo and the closeness of the multi-colored lines symbolise the connectedness of agriculture, climate action, technology, and learning.

1. The Logo

Another important aspect when it comes to logo design is its connection to the overarching Farm Demo visual identity, hence the similar graphic elements, colour scheme and lettering.

2. Corporate Colours

The Climate Farm Demo colour palette features different shades of green and yellow as colours very much present in nature and often associated with it.

Any graphic element that we build around the brand (backgrounds, graphics, icons, etc.) should preferably use this colour combination.

3. Typography and Font

The font selected for the logo is Montserrat regular (settings: ALL CAPS, tracking +250). It is a simplistic font without adornments, thus producing a clean and modern look.

Own and Editable Documents

Elaborating own and editable documents (Word reports, PPTs and so forth), these criteria apply:

- Use universal operative systems common and shared typographies that can be modified via other computers to avoid problems in the text box.
- Preferably, use Sans serif (without ornaments) and rounded fonts such as Arial, Calibri, Corbel, etc.

CLIMATE
FARM
DEMO

<https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Montserrat>

4. Logo Size

The minimum logo size recommended to avoid unreadability can be seen below.

WEB: 100 px in width

PRINT: 20 mm in width

5. Logo Protection Zone

The logo's perimeter must be protected by creating a "clean zone" that prevents "invasive" elements from getting close.

6. Logo Versions

Colour version

We will be using this version as much as possible over white backgrounds.

Greyscale version

There is also a greyscale version to be used over white or black backgrounds.

6. Logo Versions

White Version

We will use the white version over black or dark backgrounds (preferably background colours from our corporate colour palette).

6. Logo Versions

Black Version

The monochromatic black version is best suited for white or very light-coloured backgrounds.

7. Logo Over an Image or Photo

We will follow the criteria:

- Colour version only if the background allows it
- Monochromatic white or black if the final result is clearly readable after applying over the background
- Monochromatic white with a black box if the result is unreadable without it

8. Examples of Bad Logo Usage

Stretching or distorting the logo

Altering the colours of the brand's elements

8. Examples of Bad Logo Usage

Poor choice of the logo version against a background colour or unnecessary framing.

Climate Farm Demo

A EUROPEAN-WIDE NETWORK OF PILOT FARMERS
IMPLEMENTING AND DEMONSTRATING CLIMATE SMART
SOLUTIONS FOR A CARBON NEUTRAL EUROPE

Corporate Identity Manual

This project has received funding from the Horizon
Europe research and innovation programme under
Grant Agreement No 101060212.

Annex 2: Document Templates

1. Deliverable template

**Title of the document in two
 or more lines**

Subtitle in one line – optional – 2nd level

MM/January 2022

Author(s):
 Name Surname, ORGANISATION ACRONYM

This project has received funding from the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101060212.

PROJECT NAME – Climate Farm Demo
 Project Number 101060212

Project Full Title	A EUROPEAN-WIDE NETWORK OF PILOT FARMERS IMPLEMENTING AND DEMONSTRATING CLIMATE SMART SOLUTIONS FOR A CARBON NEUTRAL EUROPE
GA number	101060212
Type of Action	Coordination and Support Action (CSA)
Project Duration	64 months
Project Start Date	01.10.2022.
Project Website	climatefarmdemo.eu
Deliverable Title	{Deliverable Full Name}
Deliverable Submission Date	DD.MM.YYYY.
Status	{Draft or Final}
Dissemination Level	PU – Public or SEN – Sensitive
Deliverable Lead	{Organisation Name}
Authors	{Name (Organisation)}
Contact	{Author Contact Email}
Work Package	{WIP Number}
Keywords	{Keyword 1, Keyword 2, ...}

Disclaimer

The content of this deliverable represents the views of the author(s) only and does not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. The European Union institutions and bodies or any person acting on their behalf are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

List of Abbreviations

CFD	Climate Farm Demo
NC	National Coordinator
PDF	Pilot Farm Demo
WP	Work Package
----	----

Table of Contents

Abstract	6
Introduction	7
Title	8
Subtitle heading 2	8
SubSubtitle heading 3	8
Methodology	10
Title	11
Subtitle heading 2	11
SubSubtitle heading 3	11

List of Tables and Figures

Table 1. Example Table	8
Figure 1. Example Figure	9

Abstract

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Enim diam vulputate ut pharetra sit. Dictum at tempor commodo ullamcorper a lacus vestibulum sed arcu. Pulvinar neque laoreet suspendisse interdum consectetur libero. Eget nunc scelerisque viverra mauris in aliquam sem fringilla. Purus gravida quis blandit turpis cursus. Rhoncus aenean vel elit scelerisque mauris pellentesque pulvinar pellentesque. Donec et odio pellentesque diam volutpat commodo sed. Ultricies leo integer malesuada nunc. Sed viverra tellus in hac. Nec ultrices dui sapien eget mi proin sed. Arcu dui vivamus arcu felis bibendum ut tristique et.

Diam vulputate ut pharetra sit amet aliquam id. Diam maecenas ultricies mi eget mauris pharetra et ultrices. Pretium vulputate sapien nec sagittis aliquam malesuada bibendum arcu. Sed enim ut sem viverra. Nisi purus in mollis nunc sed id semper. Proin nibh nisi condimentum id. Enim eu turpis egestas pretium aenean pharetra magna. Velli laoreet id donec ultrices tincidunt arcu non sodales. Odio eiusmod lacina at quis risus sed vulputate. Magna sit amet purus gravida. Et malesuada fames ac turpis egestas integer eget aliquet. Euismod nisi porta lorem mollis.

Ei malesuada fames ac turpis egestas integer eget aliquet. Euismod nisi porta lorem mollis.

Chapter 1

Introduction

Describe the content of this chapter in three lines maximum. OR erase this line.

Figure 1. Example Figure

Diam vulputate ut pharetra sit amet aliquam id. Diam maecenas ultrices mi eget maurs pharetra et ultrices. Pretium vulputate sapien nec sagittis aliquam malesuada bibendum arcu. Sed enim ut sem viverra. Nisl purus in mollis nunc sed id semper. Proin nibh nisl condimentum id. Enim eu turpis egestas pretium aenean pharetra magna. Velit laoreet id donec ultrices tincidunt arcu non sodales. Odio eusmod lacinia at quis risus sed vulputate. Magna sit amet purus gravida. Et malesuada fames ac turpis egestas integer eget aliquet. Euismod nisi porta lorem mollis.

- Proin nibh nisl condimentum id
- Enim eu turpis egestas pretium
- aenean pharetra magna
- Velit laoreet id donec
- ultrices tincidunt arcu non sodales
- Odio eusmod lacinia at
- quis risus sed vulputate.

1. Proin nibh nisl condimentum id
2. Enim eu turpis egestas pretium
3. aenean pharetra magna
4. Velit laoreet id donec
5. ultrices tincidunt arcu non sodales
6. Odio eusmod lacinia at
7. quis risus sed vulputate.

Title

Subtitle heading 2

SubSubtitle heading 3

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Enim diam vulputate ut pharetra sit. Dictum at tempor commodo ullamcorper a lacus vestibulum sed arcu. Pulvinar neque laoreet suspendisse interdum consectetur libero. Eget nunc scelerisque viverra mauris in aliquam sem fringilla. Purus gravida quis blandit turpis cursus. Rhoncus aenean vel elit scelerisque mauris pellentesque pulvinar pellentesque. Donec et odio pellentesque diam volutpat commodo sed. Ultricies leo integer malesuada nunc. Sed viverra tellus in hac. Nec ultrices du sapien eget mi proin sed. Arcu du vivamus arcu felis bibendum ut tristique et.

Table 1. Example Table

	Column 01	Column 02	Column 03
Row 01			

Diam vulputate ut pharetra sit amet aliquam id. Diam maecenas ultrices mi eget maurs pharetra et ultrices. Pretium vulputate sapien nec sagittis aliquam malesuada bibendum arcu. Sed enim ut sem viverra. Nisl purus in mollis nunc sed id semper. Proin nibh nisl condimentum id. Enim eu turpis egestas pretium aenean pharetra magna. Velit laoreet id donec ultrices tincidunt arcu non sodales. Odio eusmod lacinia at quis risus sed vulputate. Magna sit amet purus gravida. Et malesuada fames ac turpis egestas integer eget aliquet. Euismod nisi porta lorem mollis.

Et malesuada fames ac turpis egestas integer eget aliquet. Euismod nisi porta lorem mollis.

Chapter 2

Methodology

Describe the content of this chapter in three lines maximum. OR erase this line.

Title

Subtitle heading 2

SubSubtitle heading 3

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Enim diam vulputate ut pharetra sit. Dictum at tempor commodo ullamcorper a lacus vestibulum sed arcu. Pulvinar neque laoreet suspendisse interdum consectetur libero. Eget nunc scelerisque viverra mauris in aliquam sem fringilla. Purus gravida quis blandit turpis cursus. Rhoncus aenean vel elit scelerisque mauris pellentesque pulvinar pellentesque. Donec et odio pellentesque diam volutpat commodo sed. Ultricies leo integer malesuada nunc. Sed viverra tellus in hac. Nec ultrices dui sapien eget mi proin sed. Arcu dui vivamus arcu felis bibendum ut tristique et.

This project has received funding from the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101060212.

2. Working document template

Document Title
Document Subtitle (optional)

M/January 2023

Author(s):
Name Surname, ORGANISATION ACRONYM

Funded by the European Union

Table of Contents

Title 1 4

SubTitle heading 2 4

SubSubtitle heading 3 5

List of Tables and Figures

Table 1. Example Table 4

Figure 1. Example Figure 5

Title 1

>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Etiam diam vulputate ut pharetra sit. Ductus at tempor commodo ullamcorper a lacus vestibulum sed arcu. Pulvinar neque laoreet suspendisse interdum consectetur libero. Eget nunc scelerisque viverra mauris in aliquam sem fringilla. Purus gravida quis blandit turpis cursus. Rhoncus aenean vel elit scelerisque mauris pellentesque pulvinar pellentesque. Donec et odio pellentesque diam volutpat commodo sed. Ultrices leo integer malesuada nunc. Sed viverra tellus in hac. Nec ultrices dui sapien eget mi proin sed. Arcu dui vivamus arcu felis bibendum ut tristique et.

SubTitle heading 2

>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Etiam diam vulputate ut pharetra sit. Ductus at tempor commodo ullamcorper a lacus vestibulum sed arcu. Pulvinar neque laoreet suspendisse interdum consectetur libero. Eget nunc scelerisque viverra mauris in aliquam sem fringilla. Purus gravida quis blandit turpis cursus. Rhoncus aenean vel elit scelerisque mauris pellentesque pulvinar pellentesque. Donec et odio pellentesque diam volutpat commodo sed. Ultrices leo integer malesuada nunc. Sed viverra tellus in hac. Nec ultrices dui sapien eget mi proin sed. Arcu dui vivamus arcu felis bibendum ut tristique et.

Diam vulputate ut pharetra sit amet aliquam id. Diam maecenas ultricies mi eget mauris pharetra et ultrices. Pretium vulputate sapien nec sagittis aliquam malesuada bibendum arcu. Sed enim ut sem viverra. Nisi purus in mollis nunc sed id semper. Proin nibh nisl condimentum id. Enim eu turpis egestas pretium aenean pharetra magna. Volutat lacus at quis risus sed vulputate. Magna sit amet purus gravida. Et malesuada fames ac turpis egestas integer eget aliquet. Euismod nisi porta lorem mollis.

Column 01	Column 02	Column 03
Page 04		

Diam vulputate ut pharetra sit amet aliquam id. Diam maecenas ultricies mi eget mauris pharetra et ultrices. Pretium vulputate sapien nec sagittis aliquam malesuada bibendum arcu. Sed enim ut sem viverra. Nisi purus in mollis nunc sed id semper. Proin nibh nisl condimentum id. Enim eu turpis egestas pretium aenean pharetra magna. Volutat lacus at quis risus sed vulputate. Magna sit amet purus gravida. Et malesuada fames ac turpis egestas integer eget aliquet. Euismod nisi porta lorem mollis.

SubSubtitle heading 3

Diam vulputate ut pharetra sit amet aliquam id. Diam maecenas ultricies mi eget mauris pharetra et ultrices. Pretium vulputate sapien nec sagittis aliquam malesuada bibendum arcu. Sed enim ut sem viverra. Nisi purus in mollis nunc sed id semper. Proin nibh nisl condimentum id. Enim eu turpis egestas pretium aenean pharetra magna. Volutat lacus at quis risus sed vulputate. Magna sit amet purus gravida. Et malesuada fames ac turpis egestas integer eget aliquet. Euismod nisi porta lorem mollis.

Figure 1. Example Figure

- Proin nibh nisl condimentum id
- Enim eu turpis egestas pretium
- aenean pharetra magna
- Volutat lacus at quis risus sed vulputate
- ultrices tristique arcu non sodales

1. Proin nibh nisl condimentum id
2. Enim eu turpis egestas pretium
3. aenean pharetra magna
4. Volutat lacus at quis risus sed vulputate
5. ultrices tristique arcu non sodales.

Funded by the European Union

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101060212.

3. Meeting agenda template

Meeting Name

Date:		Time:	
Place:			
Organiser:			
Meeting with:			

Agenda

[time] [subject]

This project has received funding from the European Union under Grant Agreement No 101060212.

 **Funded by
the European Union**

4. Meeting minutes template

1

Meeting Name

Date:		Time:	
Place:			
Scribe:			
Meeting with:			

Summary of the Meeting

Agenda Point 1
Text

Agenda Point 2
Text
...

Key Outcomes and Support Actions

Item No	Subject/Description	Result ¹	Owner	Due Date

¹ R: Risk; A: Action; I: Issue; D: Decision; S: Status.

This project has received funding from the European Union under Grant Agreement No 101060212.

5. Milestone template

<h3>Milestone Title</h3> <p>Milestone 2023</p> <p>Author(s): Name Surname, ORGANISATION ACRONYM</p> <p> Funded by the European Union</p> <p><small>This project has received funding from the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101060212.</small></p>	<p>PROJECT NAME – Climate Farm Demo Project Number: 101060212</p> <p>Project Full Title: A EUROPEANWIDE NETWORK OF PILOT FARMERS IMPLEMENTING AND DEMONSTRATING CLIMATE SMART SOLUTIONS FOR A CARBON NEUTRAL EUROPE</p> <p>QA number: 101060212</p> <p>Type of Action: Coordination and Support Action (CSA)</p> <p>Project Duration: 84 months</p> <p>Project Start Date: 01.10.2022</p> <p>Project Website: TBC</p> <p>Milestone Title: [Milestone Full Name]</p> <p>Milestone Submission Date: DD.MM.YYYY</p> <p>Status: [Draft or Final]</p> <p>Dissemination Level: PU – Public or SEN – Sensitive</p> <p>Milestone Lead organisation: [Organisation Name]</p> <p>Authors: [Name (Organisation)]</p> <p>Contact: [Author Contact Email]</p> <p>Work Package: [WP Number]</p> <p>Keywords: [Keyword 1, Keyword 2, ...]</p> <p>Disclaimer <small>The content of this document represents the views of the author(s) only and does not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. The European Union neither endorses nor disapproves any opinion expressed in this document nor is responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.</small></p>	<p>PROJECT NAME – Climate Farm Demo Project Number: 101060212</p> <h2>Means of Verification</h2>
---	--	--

<p>PROJECT NAME – Climate Farm Demo Project Number: 101060212</p> <h3>Means of Verification</h3> <p>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Enim diam vulputate ut pharetra sit. Dictum at tempor commodo ullamcorper a lacus vestibulum sed arcu. Pulvinar neque laoreet suspendisse interdum consectetur libero. Eget nunc scelerisque viverra mauris in aliquam sem fringilla. Purus gravida quis blandit turpis cursus. Rhoncus aenean vel elit scelerisque mauris pellentesque pulvinar pellentesque. Donec et odio pellentesque diam volutpat commodo sed. Ultricies leo integer malesuada nunc. Sed viverra tellus in hac. Nec ultrices dui sapien eget mi proin sed. Arcu dui vivamus arcu felis bibendum ut tristique et.</p> <p>Diam vulputate ut pharetra sit amet aliquam id. Diam maecenas ultricies mi eget mauris pharetra et ultrices. Pretium vulputate sapien nec sagittis aliquam malesuada bibendum arcu. Sed enim ut sem viverra. Nisi purus in mollis nunc sed id semper. Proin nibh nisl condimentum id. Enim eu turpis egestas pretium aenean pharetra magna. Velit laoreet id donec ultrices tincidunt arcu non sodales. Odo eiusmod lacinita et quis risus sed vulputate. Magna sit amet punis gravide. Et malesuada fames ac turpis egestas integer eget aliquet. Euismod nisi porta lorem mollis.</p>	<p> Funded by the European Union</p> <p><small>This project has received funding from the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101060212.</small></p>
---	--

6. PPT presentation template

Annex 3: NC Social Media Survey

Climate Farm Demo - Social Media Survey (WP8)

The purpose of this survey is to get some insights into the use of social media by National Coordinators and project countries in general in relation to agriculture. It will take you no more than 5 minutes. Thank you for your time!

* Required

Which organisation do you represent in the CFD project? *

Your answer

Your organisation's country: *

Your answer

Check all the social media sites actively used by your organisation. *

LinkedIn

Twitter

Facebook

Instagram

Other: _____

If your organisation uses LinkedIn, please specify the language in which most of the posts are published. *

Your answer _____

If your organisation uses Twitter, please specify the language in which most of the posts are published. *

Your answer _____

If your organisation uses Facebook, please specify the language in which most of *
the posts are published.

Your answer _____

If your organisation uses Instagram, please specify the language in which most of *
the posts are published.

Your answer _____

Please check all the social media sites that you believe are actively used by *
farmers in your country.

LinkedIn

Twitter

Facebook

Instagram

Other: _____

According to your estimation, how many farmers in your country use LinkedIn? *

	1	2	3	4	5	
None	<input type="radio"/>	Most of them				

According to your estimation, how many farmers in your country use Twitter? *

	1	2	3	4	5	
None	<input type="radio"/>	Most of them				

According to your estimation, how many farmers in your country use Facebook? *

	1	2	3	4	5	
None	<input type="radio"/>	Most of them				

According to your estimation, how many farmers in your country use Instagram? *

	1	2	3	4	5	
None	<input type="radio"/>	Most of them				

Do you have any comments/remarks concerning this topic?

Your answer _____

Submit

[Clear form](#)

Annex 4: DEC Plans on National Level

C&D Plan on National Level

Country: XYZ
Period: June 2023-June 2024

M4/January 2023

National Coordinator:
Name Surname, ORGANISATION ACRONYM

 Funded by the European Union
This project has received funding from the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101060212

Table of Contents

Background	4
Context	4
Report on c&d activities in previous period	4
CDE Plan for the period June 2023-June 2024	4
Main objectives for the period June 2023-June 2024	4
Digital communication/dissemination activities	5
Public relations / activities towards thematic or general media	5
Organisation or participation in events (both online and physical)	6
Other communication, dissemination or exploitation activities	7
Additional comments or remarks	9

List of Tables and Figures

- Table 1. List of digital communication activities for the period June 2023-June 2024 5
- Table 1. contribution/inputs needed from WPs, other WPs or specific partners 5
- Table 2. Mapping of relevant magazines, newspapers, internet portals, TV or radio shows, podcasts etc 5
- Table 2. List of PR activities 6
- Table 1. contribution/inputs needed from WPs, other WPs or specific partners 6
- Table 3. List of online and physical events 6
- Table 1. contribution/inputs needed from WPs, other WPs or specific partners 7
- Table 4. Print material 8
- Table 1. contribution/inputs needed from WPs, other WPs or specific partners 8
- Table 4. Other communication, dissemination or exploitation activities 8
- Table 1. contribution/inputs needed from WPs, other WPs or specific partners 9

Background

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Enim diam vulputate ut pharetra sit. Dictum at tempor commodo ullamcorper a lacus vestibulum sed arcu. Pulvinar neque laoreet suspendisse interdum consectetur libero. Eget nunc scelerisque viverra mauris in aliquam sem fringilla. Purus gravida quis blandit turpis cursus. Rhoncus aenean vel elit scelerisque mauris pellentesque pulvinar pellentesque. Donec et odio pellentesque diam volutpat commodo sed. Ultricies leo integer malesuada nunc. Sed viverra tellus in hac. Nec ultrices dui sapien eget mi proin sed. Arcu dui vivamus arcu felis bibendum ut tristique et.

Context

Brief explanation of national context, target groups, main communication channels etc.

Report on c&d activities in previous period

Please explain main communication and dissemination actions undertaken to promote the project and its activities in previous period.

CDE Plan for the period June 2023-June 2024

Main objectives for the period June 2023-June 2024

Brief explanation of communication and dissemination objectives for the period from June 2023 to June 2024.

Digital communication/dissemination activities

Table 1. List of digital communication activities for the period June 2023-June 2024

No	Activity (ie. article, social media post / interview / video...)	Channel (ie. Partner's website, Twitter, LinkedIn...)	Topic	Due date
1.	Raw txt			
2.				
3.				
4.				
...				

Table 2. contribution/inputs needed from WPs, other WPs or specific partners for digital DEC activities

No. of the activity from the above table	Contribution needed (ie. Specific information, template, text, visual, specific input...)	Partner or Work Package Assigned	Due date
1.	Raw txt		
2.			
3.			
4.			
...			

Public relations / activities towards thematic or general media

Table 3. Mapping of relevant magazines, newspapers, internet portals, TV or radio shows, podcasts etc

Media	Link (if applicable)	Brief description	Potential reach
Raw txt			

Table 4. List of PR activities

No	Topic of press release article	Media (list all web portals, TV or radio channels, etc you want to reach)	Due date
1	Raw txt		
2			
...			

Table 5. contribution/inputs needed from WPs, other WPs or specific partners for PR activities

No. of the activity from the above table	Contribution needed (ie. Specific information, template, text, visual, specific input...)	Partner or Work Package Assigned	Due date
1.	Raw txt		
2.			
3.			
4.			
...			

Organisation or participation in events (both online and physical)

Table 6. List of online and physical events

No	Event (ie. Webinar, press conference, participation in fairs/conferences/exhibition, meeting, presentation etc)	Description	Target audience	Partners involved	Due date
1.	Raw txt				
2.					
3.					
4.					
...					

Table 7. contribution/inputs needed from WPs, other WPs or specific partners for organisation/participation to events

No. of the activity from the above table	Contribution needed (ie. Specific information, template, text, visual, specific input, project website announcement...)	Partner or Work Package Assigned	Due date
1.	Raw txt		
2.			
3.			
4.			
...			

Linking with projects, initiatives or policy makers on local, national or regional level (connection to WP7)

Table 8. List of activities that links CFD with other projects, initiatives or policy makers

No.	Title of the activity	Description	PIPs involved	Partners involved	Due date
1.	Raw txt				
2.					
3.					
4.					
...					

Table 9. contribution/inputs needed from WPs, other WPs or specific partners for linkage with national PIPs

No. of the activity from the above table	Contribution needed (ie. Specific information, template, text, visual, specific input, project website announcement...)	Partner or Work Package Assigned	Due date
1.	Raw txt		
2.			
3.			
4.			
...			

Other communication, dissemination or exploitation activities

Table 10. Print material

No.	Type (ie. Flyer, poster, flag...)	Number of copies	Target audience	Purpose	Due date
1.	Raw txt				
2.					
3.					
...					

Table 11. contribution/inputs needed from WPs, other WPs or specific partners for print materials

No. of the activity from the above table	Contribution needed (ie. Specific information, template, text, visual, specific input, ...)	Partner or Work Package Assigned	Due date
1.	Raw txt		
2.			
3.			
4.			
...			

Table 12. Other communication, dissemination or exploitation activities

No.	Activity	Description	Target audience	Partners involved	Due date
	Raw txt				

Table 13. contribution/input needed from WPs, other WPs or specific partners for other DEC activities

No. of the activity from the above table	Contribution needed (i.e. Specific information, template, text, visual, specific input, ...)	Partner or Work Package Assigned	Due date
1.	Raw txt		
2.			
3.			
4.			
...			

Additional comments or remarks

Please write here all comments you might have.

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101060212.